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Monetary valuation of soil ecosystem services and creation of initiatives to invest in soil health: setting a framework for the inclusion of soil health in business and in the policy making process- InBestSoil

D3.2 REPORT ON ECONOMIC VALUATION OF ECOSYSTEM SERVICES AND DISSERVICES IN LHS AND LLS

FiBL

Universidade de Vigo

Report on economic valuation of ecosystem services and disservices in LHs

Executive Summary

Propose

The InBestSoil project, in its WP3, aims to give a monetary value to the ecosystem services (ES) provided by soils for different land uses. To this end the different market and non-market values across land uses and within land management scenarios have been quantitatively measured. In this context, the purpose of this deliverable (D3.2), within the InBestSoil project, is to estimate a monetary valuation of ecosystem services (ES) and disservices provided by soils under different land use scenarios. By applying a combination of market and non-market valuation methods, this report quantifies the economic value of soil-based ecosystem services across various biogeographical regions. The findings contribute to integrating soil health considerations into business models and policy-making processes.

Intended audience

This document is relevant for policymakers involved in land-use planning, environmental management, and policy development at national and EU levels. Additionally, it provides valuable insights for researchers in environmental economics, soil science, and sustainability, as well as land managers overseeing agricultural, forestry, and urban land.

Description of de main activities

The main activities carried out consist of a comprehensive methodological framework employed to assess the economic value of different ecosystem services provided by soil. Market values were estimated using cost and revenue data from cases studies (Lighthouses and Living Labs) and focus on provisioning services. Non-market values were derived using a meta-analysis of European studies and benefit transfer methodologies to value regulating and cultural ecosystem services. The study covers different land use types (agricultural, forestry, urban, and industrial soils) across multiple case studies, including different interventions to promote soil health.

Key results: Results can be divided in result regarding markets, non-market values, and comparative analysis regarding the soil use.

Martek valuation findings:

- Agricultural and forestry land uses generate significant provisioning ecosystem services with variations in profitability depending on the management practices carried out.
- Restorations efforts in degraded areas, such creation of artificial soils in mine context or reforestation of forest degrade areas, show high investment cost with long-term expected economic benefits.

Non-market valuation findings:

- Carbon sequestration, water retention, and erosion control contribute substantial indirect value to society, particularly in forest and conservation agriculture contexts.

- Cultural services, such as recreation and landscape aesthetics play a crucial role in restoration areas, as their non-market value offset, in the long term, the direct market cost of the restoration efforts.

Comparative analysis:

- Sustainable soil management practices improve both market and non-market values, reinforcing the economic justification for soil health investments.
- Industrial and mining soil restoration showed limited direct market value but provided crucial long-term environmental benefits.

Research and Practice Implications

The findings highlight the need for integrated approaches to soil ecosystem services valuation, emphasizing the economic relevance of sustainable land management that includes non-market (invisible) values. Researchers can further refine valuation methodologies, addressing gaps in cultural and regulation ecosystem service valuation, and policy makers can inform policy decisions with the real contribution of the soil to the social well-being.

Stakeholders, including farmers and landowner, can use these findings to substantiate requests for soil conservation incentives and to implement sustainable practices that yield synergistic economic and environmental benefits. Furthermore, these insights contribute to the development of a broader consensus regarding the economic value of sustainable soil management practices.

Policy Implications

The results emphasize the importance of incorporating soil ecosystem services into EU and national policy frameworks. Key recommendations include:

- Promoting incentives for sustainable soil management and restoration projects.
- Integrating non-market valuation metrics into land-use decision-making.
- Supporting research on underrepresented soil services, particularly in urban and industrial contexts.

Conclusion

This deliverable provides a comprehensive economic valuation of soil ecosystem services, reinforcing the significance of soil health investments for both private and public stakeholders. The findings will guide further research, policy development, and practical implementation, fostering new business models with a stronger link between soil conservation and economic sustainability within the InBestSoil project.

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1. Objectives

One of the goals of the WP3 of InBestSoil is to give a monetary value to the ecosystem services (ES) provided by soils under different land uses and biogeographic regions. In this context, the objective of this deliverable is to provide the total economic value of soil ecosystem services and disservices by employing a combination of market and non-market valuation methods. Market valuation methods are employed to quantify direct use values and to estimate the provisioning services. Additionally, a benefit transfer methodology is applied using a meta-analysis approach to derive non-market values for indirect use and non-use values for ESs related to soil, primarily for regulating and cultural services.

2. Introduction

Soil ecosystems play a crucial role in maintaining environmental balance as well as human well-being, primarily through the wide range of ecosystem services (ES) they provide (Jónsson et al., 2017). These services, classified according to The Millennium Ecosystem Assessment (MEA, 2005) into four different categories (provisioning, regulating, supporting, and cultural), are not only essential for human well-being but also indispensable for food security, climate regulation, and biodiversity conservation (Alcón et al., 2022). Despite their undeniable value, the economic quantification of soil ecosystem services remains limited, particularly in analyses by soil type (agricultural, forest, urban, and mining).

One of the objectives of the InBestSoil project is precisely to address this gap by providing empirical evidence to the scientific and policy audience. The project aims to contribute to this gap by estimating the total economic value of ecosystem services and disservices of soil across different land types and under varying conditions, using both market and non-market valuation methods.

The market valuation of soil services focuses on the direct economic contributions of soil through various land uses, such as agricultural, forestry, and urban practices. These values are derived from detailed technical data provided by experts, and supported by case study leaders, from InBestSoil case studies in different biogeographical regions of Europe. The data set encompasses information pertaining to inputs, labour, and production, supplemented by external statistical sources. Collectively, these elements constitute a comprehensive monetary assessment of provisioning services associated with soil.

In parallel, the non-market valuation of soil ecosystem services is carried out using a benefit transfer methodology, supported by a meta-analysis of 29 relevant European studies published between 2013 and 2024. This methodology allows for the estimation of indirect and non-use values of ecosystem services, particularly those related to soil regulation and cultural functions. The literature review allows the collection of data on soil types, ecosystem service indicators, and their economic values, focusing on already published studies. Although the review revealed a lack of studies on soil ecosystem services in mining contexts, it succeeded in generating a robust dataset for agricultural, forest, and urban soils.

By combining market and non-market valuation approaches, this deliverable provides a comprehensive economic assessment of the ecosystem services and disservices of soil, contributing to a more complete understanding of its role in sustaining ecosystems and human societies. The results not only inform policy decisions and environmental management strategies but also highlight the economic potential of soil restoration and conservation practices across various land uses in Europe.

To address its objectives, the report first outlines the methodology used to quantify the market and non-market value associated with the ecosystem services provided by soil. The results are then presented by each LH and LL, for market value and according to the category of ecosystem services (provisioning, regulating, supporting, and cultural) in the case of non-market

value. Finally, an estimation of the total economic value (market and non-market) of the ecosystem services provided by soil in each of the case studies is provided.

3. Description of the case studies used in InBestSoil to assess soil health and quantify the economic market and non-market value of the soil ecosystem services

In order to understand the different soil health indicators co-selected under a participatory approach with experts (Deliverable 3.1: Toolkit of Soil Health Indicators with Metrics), it is important to understand the characteristics of the different case studies implemented in InBestSoil project in which indicators will be used. Soil health indicators have been selected to match the specific characteristics and needs of each lighthouse (LH) and living lab (LL) included in the project, with different land uses (agricultural, forestry, urban and industrial) in four different biogeographic regions (Atlantic, Boreal, Continental, and Mediterranean). Each ES has associated an indicator.

InBestSoil is based on seven LH and two LL to develop the economic valuation of the ecosystem services associated to soil, and co-develop, co-design and decide business models based on healthy soils to foster public and private investments on soil health (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Map with the location of the lighthouses (LH) and living labs (LL) of InBestSoil, with the strategy followed in each of them.

Following the definitions given by the Implementation Plan for the Soil Mission, we consider a LH as a place for demonstration of long-term solutions, which are exemplary in their performance in terms of soil health improvement. For the establishment of LLs, we use the definition proposed by the European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL). These LLs are intended as collaborations among some research and innovation ecosystems, which involve regional stakeholders in systemic research and codesign, to jointly improve the effectiveness of new practices on soil health. The LHs are selected as representatives of the implementation of sustainable management practices that have led to high soil health under important land uses in the EU. They will act as innovation and demonstration ecosystems to accelerate the co-creation and uptake of solutions to enhance soil health in the EU, by the development of a proper ecosystem for investment and generation of business models.

Thus, each LH is based on an area with the long-term implementation of sustainable interventions to enhance soil health. In addition, each LH has also identified a nearby area with unsustainable management practices associated to low soil health, used as reference or baseline to compare soil health between two contrasting scenarios (long-term sustainable management vs unsustainable management leading to high soil health vs low soil health, respectively). As a result, these LHs are examples for demonstration solutions and engagement of practitioners and key stakeholders to accelerate the innovation uptake. Each of the two LLs include between 10 and 20 farms (agricultural land use in the Mediterranean and Continental biogeographic regions) that operate at a subregional level, in which experiments involving land managers, farmers, farmers' organizations, businesses, scientific community, policymakers, and industries, among others, are coordinated, to test, monitor and evaluate practical solutions to develop business with interventions that enhance soil health.

The rationale for the selection of the LHs and LLs to be used as innovation ecosystems is as follows: i) they are the most dominant land uses in Europe with 84.6% of the total European surface, ii) they are included in the most extensive biogeographic regions of Europe, covering 87.1% of the total surface, iii) they are a good demonstration of sustainable vs unsustainable practices to enhance soil health, which have been co-designed between wide range of actors in the value chain, and iv) they already have a community of stakeholders collaborating to make business and increase economic revenues by enhancing soil health.

To properly understand the characteristics, needs and challenges of InBestSoil LHs and LLs, we provide in Annex 1 a detailed description of each of them.

4. Methodological Framework and Data Processing

This section outlines the methodological framework and data processing steps undertaken to estimate the total economic value of soil ecosystem services and disservices in LHs and LLs. The analysis is divided into two main components: the evaluation of market values associated with land use and the estimation of non-market values ecosystem services related those uses through benefit transfer methodologies. Each component addresses specific types of ecosystem services and employs distinct approaches to data collection and analysis, ensuring a comprehensive assessment of soil ecosystem services across different land uses.

4.1 How to evaluate market values of ecosystem services.

The monetary market valuation of the various land uses across LHs and LLs has been conducted based on data provided by the expert case study leaders of each case study. Most of the technical data was gathered directly from the case study area, encompassing information on inputs (such as raw materials and water consumption), work performed, total hours worked by the workforce, and the resulting production. For each of these parameters, the associated costs and revenues were also obtained with the assistance of the expert case study leaders of each case study. This information was then supplemented and enhanced through a review of statistical portals and data from specialised literature.

To ensure the accuracy and robustness of these technical parameters and market prices, a participatory process was conducted involving various stakeholders across the Lighthouses and the Living Labs. This collaborative approach allowed for the gathering of primary data from a diverse pool of expertise, including researchers, land users, and public managers and civil society in general. The composition of the groups that assisted in the valuation process is detailed in Table 1 below, categorized by the specific case study.

Table 1: Stakeholder participation in the economic valuation process across LHs and LLs.

Name(s) of CS leader(s)	Number of people involved			
	Users	Research ers	Public Managers	Civil society
Elena de Julián / Rocío Seisdedos	3			
Virginia Sánchez-Navarro / Jorge Sánchez Navarro		1		
Javier de Rivera	2	1		
Igor Bogunovic	1	3		
Katarzyna Bogdziewicz/Paulo Pereira	5	5	3	2
Viktorija Vendiņa	3	4	5	3
Linda Calciolari	2	1		

Gianluca Carboni, Valentina Mereu	8	10	2	
Thomas Wassermann, Markus Steffens	55	10 +	3	1

Given the disparity of characteristics of each area, with different land uses, the procedure for collecting data for each case study is briefly explained below.

It is evident that each of the aforementioned LH or LL has been associated with a specific starting situation that results in compromised soil health. However, this is counterbalanced by an intervention that has been demonstrated to enhance soil health. LH1. Mediterranean Forestry Soil: Restoration of soil by rotational grazing managing in woody pastures.

The technical information obtained in this LH is based on the production of livestock (cows) and the costs related to their feeding, which was based on grain, with a water consumption of around 30 l/cow per day. Electricity consumption was also considered within the water consumption, which was around 22.75 kw/h. There is only one worker who feeds the animals. All these tasks were carried out during the year 2024.

LH2. Mediterranean Industrial Soil: Restoration of contaminated soil by metallic mining activities using artificial soils (Technosols).

The peculiarity of this LH is that the restoration activities were carried out in 2012, so the final monetary values are adjusted with a Spanish Consumer Price Index (IPC) to the year 2023. The work carried out was mainly based on the creation of technosoil and natural vegetation. A maximum of up to 7 workers were employed. In this restoration of the LH there is no marketable production.

LH3. Atlantic Industrial Soil: Restoration of contaminated soil by copper mining activities using artificial soils (Technosols).

All technical information is based on the creation of technosoil, with the use of heavy machinery and the appropriation of nutrients (N, P, K). Each transformation process requires a maximum of two employees. Regarding the income from the technosoil, it comes from the waste management by taking over the sludge and ashes.

LH4. Continental Urban Soil: Carbon sequestration and flood mitigation capacity of agricultural and forest uses in urban soils.

The technical information of this LH is based on sowing, harvesting and application of fertilisers and pesticides to the soil with the use of Tractor (93kW) + sprayer (1200L capacity). In general, there has been only one worker, and the revenue comes from the production of winter wheat (grain and straw).

LH5. Boreal Urban Soil: Impact of urban agriculture on soil health.

All raw material has been based on planting tomato seeds, with the use of Honda grass cutting machine (horsepower 4) only for cutting grass. This work has been carried out by 2 workers and the revenue comes from the production of various crops.

LH6. Boreal Forestry Soil: Effects planting strategies, fertilization, and sustainable soil management on soil health

The technical information comes from the reforestation with *Pinus sylvestris*, *Picea abies*, *Betula pendula*, *Alnus glutinosa* and from the self-care of the plantations. Up to a maximum of 25 workers have been necessary and there is no production in this LH yet.

LH7. Atlantic Agricultural Soil: Sustainable practices (crop diversification, minimum tillage, fertilization reduction...) around the inclusion of a new crop in the area: lupines

All information comes from data related to harvesting, sowing and soil fertilisation for crop production. It also includes the machinery used for ploughing, weedharrow, cultivator, hoe etc. For each of these tasks the collaboration of 1 worker has been necessary. All this information is an estimate of the average production in a normal year, using costs and revenues to the year 2024. It is therefore an estimate based on the farmer's experience over the years.

LL1. Mediterranean Agricultural Soil: Application of conservation agriculture practices, as potential climate change adaptation and mitigation strategies: effects on soil health and crop production

For LL1, 3 experimental cases have been considered as representative: RT9, CT3 and SS7. In the case of RT9, production was based on olives and wood. The amount of production is a five-year average (2019-2023), with work aimed at improving plant productivity and promoting vegetative growth and flowering + pest control. A maximum of 5 workers and machinery based on 75 Hp Tractor + fertilizer spreader and Electric chain pruner equipped with a 700W lithium battery have been used.

For CT3, production was based on grain and straw (durum wheat). Planting and fertilisation activities have been carried out with the use of Lamborghini 583 r (55hp) + spreader Lely 1500 (one disc, 24 m) and Fendt 211 (125 hp) + Gaspardo SC300 (3m). A maximum of 2 workers have been employed.

For SS7, the production was based on shredded soft wheat. The soil was planted and fertilised with Fendt 415 (114 kW + semeato TDNG 300 E) and CLAAS Jaguar 870 (430kW) using a maximum of 2 workers.

LL2. Continental Agricultural Soil: Adoption of sustainable management to enhance C sequestration and soil health

LL2 cases have been analysed: LL16-LL18, LL19-LL21 and LL22-24.

For LL16-18, production of Barley - *Hordeum Vulgare* has been obtained, carrying out work related to Slurry Fertilization, Spraying and Sowing 3cm depth. Steyr CVT 6175 + Zunhammer K12.5PUL with spreading boom, Steyr CVT 6175 + Kverneland 3m + Knoche Roller and Weidemann Hoftrac + Case ICH Farmall 95 + Rauch fertilizer spreader were used. 1 worker has been employed for each activity.

For LL19-21, a production of Hay and Silage was obtained. Work was carried out on Slurry Fertilization, Grass mowing for hay and silage using Steyr CVT 6175 + Kuhn Mower 8831 and 3221 and Steyr CVT 6175 + Zunhammer K12.5PUL with spreading boom. 1 worker was employed for each job.

For LL22-24, the production obtained was Milling Wheat. Organic fertilization, corn stubble mulching, Spraying and Plowing were carried out. Steyr CVT 6175 + manure spreader JF, Weidemann Hoftrac + Case ICH Farmall 95 + Rauch fertilizer spreader and Case ICH Farmall 95 + Holder Sprayer were used. 1 worker was employed for each activity.

The information obtained from this market valuation will form part of the provisioning ecosystem services that can take place for each land use, and whose value will also be complemented by the subsequent non-market valuation to obtain more rigorous results.

4.2 Non-Market Valuation: Data Measurement and Processing.

To conduct a comprehensive review of the non-market value of ecosystem services provided by different land uses, a literature review was carried out to identify the most relevant published studies focused on soil ecosystem services between January 2013 and April 2024. To this end, the bibliographic search engine Web of Science was used. We applied the following TS search field tags (it includes papers related topics in the title, abstract, and keywords): "economic value" and "soil" and "ecosystem service". This search criterion resulted in 312 documents, including peer-reviewed papers, working papers, thesis, and conference contributions.

In the first step, documents not written in English (or in Spanish) were excluded. In the second step, the title and abstract of each document were reviewed to perform an initial screening, eliminating those not directly related to the topic of interest. In addition, to better align with the objectives of the project, we retained only those works conducted in European countries. Finally, a thorough screening of the remaining 51 studies was conducted to assess their suitability for the meta-analysis (the ecosystem services considered in each study had to be measured using the indicators included in Deliverable 3.1, or the closest possible equivalents, and must include an estimate of their economic value). As a result of this process, 27 additional articles not initially included in the list were identified, yielding a total of 88 articles reviewed in-depth. After reviewing them, a final set of 29 articles were considered for the analysis.

The methodology applied to monetary value the contribution of soil ecosystem services to human well-being requires a combination of biophysical indicators and economic evaluation methods. The procedure described above successfully allowed us to gather both types of information: biophysical indicators to measure soil ecosystem services and the estimated economic value of these related services, as estimated by previous research for the soil types proposed in the project: agricultural, forest and urban. However, it is important to highlight that no relevant articles were found regarding soil ecosystem services in mining contexts. Figure 2 presents the analytical framework, showing the ecosystem services considered, the indicators (and units) related, and the number of observations we found measuring them.

Based on the soil ecosystem service value assessment system in Figure 2, we collected data from the literature including details such as the title, author, study period, geographic region, type of soil, the ecosystem service, the units of the indicator to measure each ecosystem service, the economic value and the valuation method applied. Additionally, based on the geographic location of the studies analysed, each sampled study was supplemented with data on the temperature and precipitation levels of the region where it was conducted.

Our sampling, based on previous studies, enabled us to create a database composed of 189 observations, which include indicators to measure nearly all the ecosystem services promoted by soil that were considered in Deliverable 3.1 (Toolkit of Soil Health Indicators with Metrics). In particular, we did not find information on biodiversity, which belongs to supporting ecosystem service category, and cultural identity, which belongs to the cultural ecosystem services category. A deeper understanding of the ecosystem services and the proposed indicators to measure them are found in Deliverable 3.1). Nevertheless, not all proposed indicators for each of the included ecosystem services were found in the studies reviewed. Table 2 presents the selected references along with the analysed indicators in each study and the type of soil considered in the analysis.

	Ecosystem service	Biophysical indicator (units)	Observed
Provisioning	Food	Crop yield (Kg/ha)	18
	Fiber, energy or raw materials	Plant biomass (Kg/ha)	11
	Water	Water content (m³/ha)	12
Regulating	Climate regulation	C sequestration (Tn/ha)	54
		Soil CO ₂ emissions (Tn/ha)	7
		Total ecosystem organic content TCE (Tn/ha)	1
	Water/air purification and soil contaminant reduction	Pollution of surface or groundwater by nitrates (Mg/L/ha)	6
	Nutrient cycling	Available macronutrients (P, K, Ca, Mg, S) (Kg/ha)	4
	Flood regulation and water storage	Soil's water retention capacity (m³/ha)	7
	Erosion control	Soil erosion rate (Tn/ha)	13
Bare soil (%)		5	
Supporting	Biodiversity		
	Habitat for organism (landscape heterogeneity)	Presence of natural green elements (%)	3
Cultural	Heritage	Presence of cultural elements (Yes/No)	4
	Identity		
	Recreation	Recreation index (1-7)	1
		Visitors and accommodations (n^o)	4
	Aesthetics	Aesthetics landscape index (1-10)	25
	Information for cognitive development	Employment generation (AWU/ha)	5

Figure 2: Analytical framework

Table 2: Selected references and indicators.

Indicator	Provisioning			Regulating							Supporting	Cultural					
	Croop yield	Plant biomass	Water content	C sequestration	Soil CO2 emissions	Total ecosystem organic content TCE	Pollution of surface or groundwater by nitrates	Available macronutrients (P, K, Ca, Mg, S)	Soil' s water retention capacity	Soil erosion rate	Vegetation cover	Presence of natural green elements	Presence of cultural elements	Recreation index	Visitors and accommodations	Aesthetics landscape index	Employment generation
Reference																	
<i>Hansen and Malmaeus (2016)</i>	X	X				X											
<i>Alcon et al. (2022)</i>	X			X			X			X			X			X	X
<i>Jónsson et al., 2017</i>	X			X			X										
<i>Dominati et al., 2014</i>	X				X		X	X	X								
<i>Alam et al., 2014</i>	X	X		X				X									
<i>Makrickas et al. (2023)</i>		X	X		X												
<i>Gren et al. (2020)</i>		X															
<i>Porter (2009)</i>		X		X					X								
<i>Morri et al. (2014)</i>			X	X						X							
<i>Johnson and Geisendorf (2019)</i>			X	X							X				X		
<i>Mastorille et al. (2018)</i>			X							X							
<i>Mäntymaa et al. (2023)</i>				X													X
<i>Franceschinis et al. (2022)</i>				X													
<i>Vermaat et al. (2020)</i>				X													
<i>Aslam et al. (2017)</i>				X													

<i>Riccioli et al. (2020)</i>		X			
<i>De Valck et al. (2019)</i>		X	X		X
<i>Rodriguez-Entrena et al. (2012)</i>		X			
<i>Tardieu et al., (2013)</i>		X			
<i>Morri and Sautolini (2022)</i>				X	
<i>Brander et al. (2018)</i>					X
<i>Tyrväinene, L et al. (2014)</i>					X
<i>Tyrväinene, L et al. (2021)</i>					X
<i>Zandersen and Tol (2009)</i>					X
<i>Fredman (2013)</i>					X
<i>Silverio et al. (2021)</i>					X
<i>Bernués et al. (2015)</i>					X
<i>Bernués et al. (2014)</i>					X

The study of the economic valuation of ecosystem services through the value transfer method, particularly using meta-regression analysis, typically considers the estimated economic value as the dependent variable and the indicator used to measure the ecosystem service as the independent variable. Additionally, control variables may be incorporated to ensure that the relationship between the indicator and the economic value is not biased. The independent and dependent variables used in this study are described below:

Economic Value: This refers to the economic value of a specific ecosystem service provided by soil, expressed in euros per hectare. The economic value of ecosystem services is often influenced by socio-economic factors like GDP (Teoh et al., 2019). Hence, to ensure consistency and comparability across the diverse economic and temporal contexts of the data, the economic value was standardized using the Purchasing Power Parity (PPP) correction factor, as provided by the World Bank's World Development Indicators. All values were subsequently expressed in 2024 euros. This approach was adopted for two primary reasons. First, the dataset includes information from multiple European countries, each with varying levels of purchasing power, necessitating an adjustment to account for these disparities. Second, the data spans a 12-year period, making it essential to correct for price changes over time to reflect a uniform economic context. This methodological approach ensures that the estimated values are not biased by differences in purchasing power or temporal price variations, thereby providing a robust basis for comparison and analysis within the scope of this research.

Indicator: Each indicator represents a quantifiable and measurable attribute of a system, serving as a proxy for specific ecosystem services (Layke et al., 2012). These indicators are used to quantify the contribution of soil to the respective ecosystem service, ultimately providing a numerical value for that service (Luján-Soto et al., 2020). The indicators have been thoroughly defined in Deliverable 3.1 (Toolkit of Soil Health Indicators with Metrics) For a more detailed description and deeper understanding of these indicators, please refer to that document. A subset of these indicators has been utilized in this study. To identify possible nonlinear relationships between the ecosystem service indicator and its estimated economic value, the squared term of the indicator has also been considered in some cases. This approach allows for the exploration of potential diminishing or increasing marginal effects of the indicator on its economic value, ensuring that any curvilinear trends are accurately captured.

Land use: This refers to the land use, which may be agricultural, forest, or urban. As previously noted, no articles addressing ecosystem services associated with mining soils were identified. However, this is not a limitation, as our project includes two case studies on mining soils, but the intervention focuses on their rehabilitation, which typically results in forest uses. Land use is included as a binary variable, taking the value of 1 if the considered ecosystem service pertains to a given land use, and 0 otherwise. Therefore, three dummy variables are included (one for each land use).

Temperature: Refers to the annual average temperature of the location where the analysed study was conducted (in °C).

Precipitation: Refers to the average annual accumulated precipitation of the location where the study was conducted (in mm/year).

To conduct the meta-regression, the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) method was employed, which is widely used in econometric analysis (Nie et al., 2023). For each of the ES considered we estimated the following regression model.

$$Y_i^j = \beta_0 + \sum_{i=1}^n \gamma_i CV_i + \beta_1 indicator_i + \beta_2 Sagri_i + \beta_3 Sforest_i + \varepsilon_i$$

Where Y is economic value in euros per hectare; CV are control variables (temperature and precipitation); *indicator* refers to the indicator associated with the ES valued (Figure 2); *Sagri* is a dummy for agricultural use (1 if the land use considered is agricultural and 0 if not); *Sforest* is a dummy for forest use (1 if the land use considered is forest and 0 if not).

Three key specifications of the estimation model must be highlighted. First, during the model estimation process, several tests were conducted to determine the most appropriate measurement units for the dependent variable, ensuring the best possible fit to the observed data. Consequently, for some ecosystem services, the dependent variable is expressed in natural logarithmic form, while for others, the original base value is retained. Additionally, in cases where necessary to achieve a better fit to the observed data, the squared term of the indicator variable was included in the regression models. This approach enhances the model's ability to accurately reflect reality.

Second, regarding the land use for which the ES value is estimated. In an initial step we introduced dummy variables for each land use (urban soil serves as the reference category) as proposed in the previous equation. Subsequently, only when the coefficient associated with the land use is statistically significant, we explored the mediating effects of land use on the estimated economic value of the ES. For this purpose, an interaction term is introduced to capture the relationship between the ecosystem service and the land use (*indicator × Sagri* or *indicator × Sforest*).

Third, for some ES, information was available from only one or a limited number of empirical studies, making it impossible to perform a regression model. In such cases, a direct benefit transfer method was applied, drawing directly from the findings of the available studies.

5. Market and non-market value of soil ecosystem services

5.1 Market values for each LH and LL

In this section we provide the market valuation for each LH and LL. This valuation makes it possible to obtain a first value of the provisioning ecosystem service for each case study, identified based on the information provided by expert and case study leaders. For each LL and LH Investment, Operational and Maintenance (O&M) costs are estimated together with the annual revenues related to production, if any.

The values of costs and revenues have been estimated considering the size of the case study. At this stage, investment costs are reported as total values and are not annualized. This approach is intentional, as the objective of this section is to present the full magnitude of the investments required. In subsequent sections, when quantifying the total economic value (market and non-market values), investment costs are converted into annual equivalent costs following standard accounting practices. This annualization accounts for the long-term nature of the investments, assuming a technosol lifetime comparable to that of a building (68 years), thereby ensuring consistency in the economic valuation framework.

5.1.1 LH1. Mediterranean Forestry Soil: Restoration of soil by rotational grazing managing in woody pastures.

LH1.1. Mediterranean Forestry Soil: Restoration of soil by rotational grazing managing in woody pastures

	Performed work	Amount	Units	Water amount (m ³)	Total working hours	Cost (€)	Revenue (€)
Investment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
O&M	Feeding animals	102,405	kg	640,170	1,050	58,764	-
Production	Meat cows	9,640	kg	-	-	-	40,609
TOTAL (€/ 232 ha) - 2024						58,764	40,609
TOTAL (€/ ha) - 2024						253	175

LH1.2. Reforestation, continuous tillage and lack of livestock

	Performed work	Amount	Units	Water amount (m ³)	Total working hours	Cost (€)	Revenue (€)
Investment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
O&M	Tree pruning and firebreaks	-	-	-	-	3,600	-
Production	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
TOTAL (€/ 20 ha) - 2024						3,600	-
TOTAL (€/ ha) - 2024						180	-

5.1.2. LH2. Mediterranean Industrial Soil: Restoration of contaminated soil by metallic mining activities using artificial soils (Technosols).

	Performed work	Amount	Units	Water amount (m ³)	Total working hours	Cost (€)	Revenue (€)
Investment	Tillage and Surface levelling	14,095	m ²	-	16	17,733	-
	Application of marble waste	95,000	kg	-	5	2,935	-
	Application of pig slurry	60	m ³	-	5	4,450	-
	Application of manure	24,000	kg	-	5	4,450	-
	Plantation	14,000	plants/ha	-	16	26,000	-
	Sowing	18,000	plants/ha	-	6	26,000	-
	Irrigation	-	-	-	200	6	50,000
O&M	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Production	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
TOTAL (€/ 1.5 ha) - 2012						131,568	-

TOTAL (€/ ha) - 2012	87,712	-
TOTAL (€/ 1.5 ha) - 2024	152,619.7	-
TOTAL (€/ ha) - 2024	101,746.5	-

5.1.3. LH3. Atlantic Industrial Soil: Restoration of contaminated soil by copper mining activities using artificial soils (Technosols).

	Performed work	Amount	Units	Water amount (m ³)	Total working hours	Cost (€)	Revenue (€)
Investment	Producing compost (including mixing with three additional raw materials to produce technosoil)	2400	Ton	-	495	42,321.65	-
	Turning and mixing activities	-	-	-	16	14,328.89	-
	Sieving	-	-	-	7	16,000.91	-
	Loading the trucks	-	-	-	42	12,409.84	-
	Transporting the technosoil	-	-	-	75	29,474.67	-
	Spreading the technosoil	-	-	-	12.5	15,257.28	-
O&M	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Production	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
TOTAL (€/ 1 ha) - 2024						129,790	-
TOTAL (€/ ha) - 2024						129,790	-

5.1.4. LH4. Continental Urban Soil: Carbon sequestration and flood mitigation capacity of agricultural and forest uses in urban soils.

5.1.4.1. LH4.1. Mulching, low soil disturbance, permanent grass cover, appropriate fertilisation

	Performed work	Amount	Units	Water amount (m ³)	Total working hours	Cost (€)	Revenue (€)
Investment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
O&M	Fertilizer application	400	kg/ha	-	21	1030	-
	Pesticide application	9.2	Kg/ha	-	40	1,453	-
	Mulching	-	-	-	4	120	-
	Pruning	-	-	-	64	1,920	-
	Harvest	-	-	-	26	1,892.8	-
Production	Apple	21	Ton/ha	-	-	-	11,130
TOTAL (€/ 1 ha) - 2024						6,416	11,130
TOTAL (€/ ha) - 2024						6,416	11,130

5.1.4.2. LH4.5. Rotations of winter wheat, winter barley, winter oats, soybean, maize. Conventional tillage, intensive mineral fertilization, absence of cover cropping, absence of mulching

	Performed work	Amount	Units	Water amount (m ³)	Total working hours	Cost (€)	Revenue (€)
Investment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
O&M	Fertilizer application	600	Kg/ha	-	18	10,013	-
	Pesticide application	1	L/ha	-	18	2,530	-
	Ploughing	-	-	-	26	2,756	-
	Harrowing	-	-	-	24	2,544	-
	Sowing	-	-	-	20	2,125	-
	Liquid fertilizer application	5	Kg/ha	-	9	850	-
	Harvest	-	-	-	30	2,184	-

Production	Winter wheat (grain)	85	Ton/ha	-	-	-	14,573
TOTAL (€/17 ha) - 2024						23,002	14,573
TOTAL (€/ ha) - 2024						1,353	857

5.1.5. LH5. Boreal Urban Soil: Impact of urban agriculture on soil heath.

5.1.5.1. LH5.1. Cucumber, tomato, onion, pumpkins and strawberries. Compost addition, mulching, no tillage, no agrochemicals use.

	Performed work	Amount	Units	Water amount (m ³)	Total working hours	Cost (€)	Revenue (€)
Investment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
O&M	Planting	10	kg	150	144	5,125	-
Production	Beetroot	12	kg	-	-	-	19.08
	Carrots	8	kg	-	-	-	7.92
	Beans	15	kg	-	-	-	2.85
	Tomatoes	50	kg	-	-	-	29
	Cucumbers	15	kg	-	-	-	24
	Potatoes	70	kg	-	-	-	98
	Onions	15	kg	-	-	-	22.5
	Strawberries	10	kg	-	-	-	33.6
	Garlic	2	kg	-	-	-	9.98
	Zucchini	20	kg	-	-	-	88
TOTAL (€/1 ha) - 2024						5,125	334.93
TOTAL (€/ ha) - 2024						5,125	334.93

5.1.5.2. LH5.2. Quercus Robur forest with reduced grass management

	Performed work	Amount	Units	Water amount (m ³)	Total working hours	Cost (€)	Revenue (€)
Investment	Planting	-	-	-	1,000	5,328.54	-
O&M	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Production	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
TOTAL (€/1.19 ha) - 2024						5,328.54	-
TOTAL (€/ ha) - 2024						4,478	-

5.1.5.3. LH5.3. *Leotodum taraxacoides* with reduced grass management, addition of compost and no agrochemicals use

	Performed work	Amount	Units	Water amount (m ³)	Total working hours	Cost (€)	Revenue (€)
Investment	Planting	-	-	-	100	402.99	-
O&M	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Production	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
TOTAL (€/ 0.09 ha) - 2024						402.99	-
TOTAL (€/ ha) - 2024						4,478	-

5.1.5.4. LH5.4. *Leotodum taraxacoides* with intensive grass management

	Performed work	Amount	Units	Water amount (m ³)	Total working hours	Cost (€)	Revenue (€)
Investment	Planting	-	-	-	800	4,298.65	-
O&M	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Production	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
TOTAL (€/0.96 ha) - 2024						4,298.65	-
TOTAL (€/ ha) - 2024						4,477.8	-

5.1.6. LH6. Boreal Forestry Soil: Effects planting strategies, fertilization, and sustainable soil management on soil health.

	Performed work	Amount	Units	Water amount (m ³)	Total working hours	Cost (€)	Revenue (€)
Investment	Quarry restoration plan	-	-	-	-	7,500	-
	Recultivation	-	-	-	42	17,030	-
	Planting	465	plants/ha	-	3	375.3	-
	Soil conditioning	0.7	kg/plant	-	4	80	-
O&M	Agro-technical care	-	-	-	3	329	-
	Protection of the generations	10	l/ha	-	8	129	-
Production	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
TOTAL (€/6.225 ha) - 2024						25,068	-
TOTAL (€/ ha) - 2024						4,027	-

5.1.7. LH7. Atlantic Agricultural Soil: Sustainable practices (crop diversification, minimum tillage, fertilization reduction...) around the inclusion of a new crop in the area: lupines.

5.1.7.1. LH7.2. Conventional

	Performed work	Amount	Units	Water amount (m ³)	Total working hours	Cost (€)	Revenue (€)
Investment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
O&M	Winter barley normal seed + fungicides	160	Kg/ha	-	-	104	-
	Fertilisation	140	KgN/ha	-	-	115	-
	Pest management	5.35	Kg,l	-	-	249	-
	Fuel	133	l	-	-	158	-
	Land rental	1	Ha	-	-	620	-
	Soil preparation	-	-	-	4.3	344	-
	Fertilizing	-	-	-	0.6	54	-
	Sowing/planting	-	-	-	0.9	72	-
	Crop protection	-	-	-	1.3	97.50	-
	Harvesting	-	-	-	3.1	372	-
	N-mineral sample	-	-	-	-	18	-
	Drying barley	7.5	Ton	-	-	28	-
	Handling	7.5	Ton	-	-	75	-
Production	Browing-Barley	9,000	Kg/ha	-	-	-	2,160
	Straw	4,800	Kg/ha	-	-	-	253
TOTAL (€/ha) - 2024						2,306	2,413
TOTAL (€/ ha) - 2024						2,306	2,413

L5.1.7. LH7.1. Linge Hof. Wide crop rotations, reduced tillage, N fixers, green manures.

	Performed work	Amount	Units	Water amount (m ³)	Total working hours	Cost (€)	Revenue (€)
Investment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
O&M	Seeds	190	Kg/ha	-	-	1,597	-
	Fertilisation	8	m ³ /ha	-	-	480	-
	Fuel	76.45	l/ha	-	-	541	-
	Seeding green manure	-	-	-	4	320	-
	Eco-ploughing	-	-	-	4	320	-
	Manure spreader	-	-	-	7	840	-
	Seeding	-	-	-	4	320	-
	Soil preparation + weeding	-	-	-	14	1,120	-
	Reseeding	-	-	-	2	160	-
	Combining (harvest)	-	-	-	4	480	-
	Drying barley	30 Ton				112.5	
	Land rental					3,720	
Production	Main product	1,500	Kg	-	-	-	5400
	Straw	1,000	Kg	-	-	-	420
TOTAL (€/6 ha) – 2024						10,090*	5,820**
TOTAL (€/ ha) – 2024						1,681*	970**
*Total cost has been estimated on average farm labour inputs used and machinery valued at 2024 prices.							
**Average production values are used valued at 2024 prices.							

5.1.8. LL1. Mediterranean Agricultural Soil: Application of conservation agriculture practices, as potential climate change adaptation and mitigation strategies: effects on soil health and crop production

5.1.8.1. LL1.11. Olive groves

RTg							
	Performed work	Amount	Units	Water amount (m3)	Total working hours	Cost (€)	Revenue (€)
Investment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
O&M	Pruning	-	-	-	12	300	-
	Pruning residuals management	-	-	-	6	300	-
	Transfer	-	-	-	-	452	-
	Soil fertilization	300	kg	-	0.15	210	-
	Fertilization and Pest control	2.35	kg	-	0.15	80	-
	Tillage	-	-	-	2.15	50	-
	Suckers' removal	-	-	-	1.30	37.5	-
	Pest control	38.05	Kg	-	0.30	132	-
	Harvest	-	-	-	45	562	-
Production	Olives	987	Kg	-	-	-	2566
	Wood	300	Kg	-	-	-	54
TOTAL (€/ 0.75 ha) - 2024						1,593	2,620
TOTAL (€/ ha) - 2024						2,124	3,493

5.1.8.2. LL1.5. Conventional tillage (durum wheat/legume)

CT3							
	Performed work	Amount	Units	Water amount (m ³)	Total working hours	Cost (€)	Revenue (€)
Investment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
O&M	weeding	4.2	l	-	1	52.5	-
	sowing + fertilization	249	kg	-	2.60	90	-
	fertilization	168	kg	-	4.30	100.8	-
	weeding	-	-	-	2.30	11.2	-
Production	grain (durum wheat)	5.8	Ton	-	-	-	1,821
	straw (durum wheat)	4	Ton	-	-	-	200
TOTAL (€/ 1.4 ha) - 2024						254	2,021
TOTAL (€/ ha) - 2024						182	1,443

5.1.8.3. LL1.8. Sod seeding (soft wheat /maize wholemeal sheredded)

SS7							
	Performed work	Amount	Units	Water amount (m ³)	Total working hours	Cost (€)	Revenue (€)
Investment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
O&M	sowing (soft wheat)	1,520	kg	-	6.5	466	-
	weeding post emergence	10	L	-	2.5	325	-
	fertilization	480	m ³	-	-	168	-
	fertilization	1,600	kg	-	-	960	-
	harvest	-	-	-	-	6	360
Production	shredded soft wheat	315.4	Ton	-	-	-	12379.45
TOTAL (€/ 8 ha) - 2024						2,279	99,036
TOTAL (€/ ha) - 2024						285	12,380

5.1.9. LL2. Continental Agricultural Soil: Adoption of sustainable management to enhance C sequestration and soil health

5.1.9.1. LL2.2. Biodynamic system

LL2 1-3							
	Performed work	Amount	Units	Water amount (m3)	Total working hours	Cost (€)	Revenue (€)
Investment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
O&M	Mulching	-	-	-	4	150	-
	Stubble ploughing	-	-	-	6	180	-
	Sowing of faba bean and Triticale	90 Beans and 80Triticcal	kg	-	6	680	-
	Fertilization	490	Kg	-	3	12,870	-
	Compost Tea application	200	l	-	1	360	-
Production	Faba bean	7,120	kg	-	-	-	8,032
	Triticale	2,030	kg	-	-	-	1,706
TOTAL (€/ 2 ha) - 2024						14,516	9,738
TOTAL (€/ ha) - 2024						7,258	4,869

5.1.9.2. LL2.2. Biodynamic system

LL2 4-6							
	Performed work	Amount	Units	Water amount (m3)	Total working hours	Cost (€)	Revenue (€)
Investment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
O&M	Stubble ploughing (6cm depth)	-	-	-	3	90	-
	Wing cultivation (flat)	-	-	-	2	60	-
	Sowing	115	Kg/ha	-	2	760	-
	Fertilization	287	Kg	-	2	9,471	-
	Mechanic weed control	-	-	-	-	1	35

Production	Mountainlentils + naked oats	2,500	kg	-	-	-	12,770
	TOTAL (€/ 1.3 ha) - 2024						10,554
TOTAL (€/ ha) - 2024						8,118	9,823

5.1.9.3. LL2.2. Biodynamic system

LL2 7-9							
	Performed work	Amount	Units	Water amount (m3)	Total working hours	Cost (€)	Revenue (€)
Investment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
O&M	flat subble ploughing	-	-	-	2	60	-
	Sowing	-	-	-	2	60	-
Production	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
TOTAL (€/ 0.3 ha) - 2024						120	-
TOTAL (€/ ha) - 2024						400	-

5.1.9.4. LL2.2. Biodynamic system

LL2 10-12							
	Performed work	Amount	Units	Water amount (m3)	Total working hours	Cost (€)	Revenue (€)
Investment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
O&M	stubble ploughing	-	-	-	2	60	-
	cultivation for seedbed	-	-	-	2	60	-
	Planting	-	-	-	7	210	-
	Sowing	22	Kg	-	2	460	-
	Fertilization	165	kg	-	1	5,445	-
	plant protection	8.4	l	-	3	390	-
	Mechanic weed control	-	-	-	-	2	60
Mulching	-	-	-	-	5	150	-

Production	Potatoes	30	ton	-	-	-	3,256
TOTAL (€/ 0.6 ha) - 2024						6,835	3,256
TOTAL (€/ ha) - 2024						11,392	5,427

5.1.9.5. LL2.2. Biodynamic system

LL2 13-15							
	Performed work	Amount	Units	Water amount (m3)	Total working hours	Cost (€)	Revenue (€)
Investment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
O&M	Surface Composting with ferment liquid	-	-	-	2	60	-
	flat harrowing for seedbed	-	-	-	2	60	-
	Sowing for Labyrinth	500	Kg	-	4	1,454	-
	Fertilization	1,035	kg	-	2	16,708	-
Production	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
TOTAL (€/ 2 ha) - 2024						18,282	0
TOTAL (€/ ha) - 2024						9,141	0

5.1.9.6. LL2.1. Conventional system with an organic and mineral fertilization

LL2 16-18							
	Performed work	Amount	Units	Water amount (m3)	Total working hours	Cost (€)	Revenue (€)
Investment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
O&M	Slurry Fertilization	23.09	m ³	-	0.5	534	-
	Stubble Cultivation 10cm depth	14,800	kg	-	4	130	-
	Sowing 3cm depth	325 grains	m ³	-	2	794	-
	Spraying	4.72	kg	-	9	723	-
	Mineral fertilization	195.96	Kg	-	4	6,705	-

Production	Barley - Hordeum Vulgare	15,032	kg	-	-	-	2,555
	TOTAL (€/ 9.2 ha) - 2024					8,886	2,555
TOTAL (€/ ha) - 2024					966	277	

5.1.9.7. LL2.1 Conventional system with an organic and mineral fertilization

LL2 19-21							
	Performed work	Amount	Units	Water amount (m3)	Total working hours	Cost (€)	Revenue (€)
Investment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Slurry Fertilization	58.94	m ³	-	0.5	1,221	-
O&M	Grass mowing for hay	14,800	kg	-	0.5	2,616	-
	Slurry Fertilization	58.94	m ³	-	2	1,251	-
	Grass mowing for silage	7,350	kg	-	3	1,399	-
	Slurry Fertilization	58.94	m ³	-	0.5	1,221	-
Production	Hay and Silage	32,100	kg	-	-	-	16,050
TOTAL (€/ 29.5 ha) - 2024					8,894	16,050	
TOTAL (€/ ha) - 2024					301	544	

5.1.9.8. LL2.1 Conventional system with an organic and mineral fertilization

LL2 22-24							
	Performed work	Amount	Units	Water amount (m3)	Total working hours	Cost (€)	Revenue (€)
Investment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	corn stubble mulching			-	0.5	70	-
O&M	organic fertilization	20,390	kg	-	1	16,692	-
	Plowing			-	0.5	190	-
	Sowing 4cm depth	350	m ²	-	1	822	-
	Spraying	1.32	l	-	1	126.2	-
	Fertilization	48.09	kg		0.5	1,651	
	Fertilization	46.92	kg		0.5	1,611.2	
Fertilization	46.92	kg		0.5	1,612		

Production	Milling Wheat	15,302	kg	-	-	-	4,805
	TOTAL (€/ 10.2 ha) - 2024						22,775
TOTAL (€/ ha) - 2024						2,233	471

5.2 Non-market values for each LH and LL

The results of the regression analysis for provisioning ecosystem services are presented in Table 3, while those for regulating ecosystem services are shown in Table 4, and Table 5 contains the results for cultural ecosystem services. Additionally, the indicators for which the direct benefit transfer method was used to estimate the economic value of associated to the ecosystem service are included in Table 6.

Table 3: Results of the regression analysis for provisioning ecosystem services

Ecosystem service	Food		Fiber, energy or raw materials		Water	
Indicator	Crop yield		Plant biomass		Water content ^a	
	Coeff.	t-value	Coeff.	t-value	Coeff.	t-value
<i>Independent variables</i>						
Indicator	0.301 **	2.00	0.0004***	10.88	0.00003 ***	5.33
Indicator ²	-6.67 e ⁻⁷	-0.20	-0.002	-0.88	-2.70 e ⁻¹¹ ***	-5.26
Sagri	-2395.71	-0.58	137.912	0.58	<i>Omitted^b</i>	
Sforest	<i>Omitted^b</i>		<i>Omitted^b</i>		7.541 ***	4.79
IndicatorXSagri						
IndicatorXSforest					0.00008 **	2.59
temperature	228.520	0.67	-68.460	-0.80	0.412 ***	6.51
precipitation	-0.731	-0.36	0.554	0.98	0.0003 ***	5.55
constant	-477.644	-0.20	-23.558	-0.44		
F-value (probability)	24.79 (0.000)		28.31 (0.001)		803.93 (0.000)	
Number of obs	18		11		12	
R ²	0.912		0.966		0.999	
*p-value < 0.01; **p-value < 0.05; ***p-value < 0.10						
^a Dependent variable in logarithmic form.						
^b Omitted because no indicators are observed within this land use.						

As can be observed, for the three identified indicators measuring the provisioning ecosystem service (food; fiber, energy or raw materials, and water), the indicator has a positive and statistically significant impact on economic value. Furthermore, this positive relationship is not linear in the case of crop yield and water content as the level of provision increases, the incremental economic value of the associated ecosystem service decreases.

Notably, for water provision, the estimated value of this ecosystem service is higher for forest soils compared to agricultural or urban soils. Additionally, forest soils positively influence the impact of the indicator on the estimated economic value, as reflected by the coefficient of the interaction term "IndicatorXSforest".

Table 4: Results of the regression analysis for regulating ecosystem services

Ecosystem service	Climate regulation		Water/air purification and soil contaminant reduction		Flood regulation and water storage		Erosion control			
Indicator	CO ₂ Sequestration ^{a,c}		Pollution of surface or groundwater by nitrates		Soil's water retention capacity ^a		Soil erosion rate ^a		Bare soil	
	Coeff.	t-value	Coeff.	t-value	Coeff.	t-value	Coeff.	t-value	Coeff.	t-value
<i>Independent variables</i>										
Indicator	0.042 *	1.67	-1.806 *	-6.68	0.0003 **	43.98	0.0002 *	3.82	-4.404 **	-8.94
Indicator ²	-0.0004 *	-1.68	0.001	0.52	-2.79 e ⁻⁹ **	-38.85	-2.82 e ⁻⁹ ***	-3.38	0.030 **	8.08
Sagri	-1.035	-1.34	Omitted ^b		Omitted ^b		Omitted ^b		Omitted ^b	
Sforest	-0.486	-0.44	Omitted ^b		Omitted ^b		Omitted ^b		Omitted ^b	
IndicatorXSagri	0.049 **	2.27			0.0031 **	16.42				
IndicatorXSforest	0.048 *	1.76								
temperature	0.283 ***	3.90	40.427 *	11.53	1.2534 *	41.40	0.710	2.34	Omitted	
precipitation	-0.00001	-0.10	0.508 **	38.91	-0.002 *	-6.48	-0.003	-0.81	Omitted	
constant	0.445	0.39	-825.57 **	-12.90	-8.592 **	50.72	-2.311	-2.20	168.13 ***	10.37
F-value (probability)	9.77 (0.000)		1497.91 (0.019)		12556.57 (0.007)		115.57 (0.008)		186.13 (0.005)	
Number of obs	54		6		7		7		5	
R ²	0.6346		0.999		0.999		0.995		0.995	

*p-value < 0.01; **p-value < 0.05; ***p-value < 0.10

^aDependent variable in logarithmic form.

^bOmitted because no indicators are observed within this land use.

^c Soil CO₂ emissions were valued using the same meta-regression framework applied to Soil CO₂ sequestration. This approach ensures methodological consistency and allows the estimation of the net soil CO₂ balance (the difference between CO₂ sequestered and CO₂ emitted by the soil).

Regarding regulating ecosystem services, it is observed that the indicators: "carbon sequestration", "soil's water retention capacity", and "soil erosion rate" (to measure climate regulation, flood regulation and water storage and erosion control ESs respectively, have a positive impact on the estimated economic value of the related ecosystem services. However, this positive relationship is not linear; as the indicator level increases, its positive impact on the economic value of the associated ecosystem service diminishes. Additionally, it is observed that only for the Climate Regulation ES does land use influence the economic value, with higher estimates associated with agricultural or forest land uses compared to urban uses (the reference category). The valuation of Soil CO₂ emissions is addressed using a harmonized regression-based approach consistent with that applied to Soil CO₂ sequestration.

The ecosystem service of water/air purification and soil contaminant reduction is measured by the indicator "pollution of surface or groundwater by nitrates." As observed, this represents a disservice. Thus, the indicator is negatively associated with economic value; in other words, higher water pollution corresponds to lower economic value for the ecosystem service. For the indicator "bare soil" which measures the percentage of soil with no vegetation, the coefficient associated is negative. This is because the indicator acts as a disservice. Additionally, it is observed that the quadratic effect is positive and statistically significant, indicating that the value associated with the disservice decreases as the percentage of bare soil increases.

Table 5: Results of the regression analysis for cultural ecosystem services

Ecosystem service	Aesthetics		Information for cognitive development	
	<i>Aesthetics landscape index</i>		<i>Employment generation^a</i>	
<i>Indicator</i>	Coeff.	<i>t-value</i>	Coeff.	<i>t-value</i>
<i>Independent variables</i>				
<i>Indicator</i>	1530.63 ***	2.84	9.001 **	17.64
<i>Indicator²</i>	<i>Excluded^c</i>		-20.724	-0.68
<i>Sagri</i>	-25266.4 ***	-5.90	<i>Omitted^b</i>	
<i>Sforest</i>	-25450.2 ***	-5.86	<i>Omitted^b</i>	
<i>IndicatorXSagri</i>				
<i>IndicatorXSforest</i>				
<i>temperature</i>	-135.7	0.746	-0.121	-0.55
<i>precipitation</i>	-20.232	0.156	-0.003	-0.45
<i>constant</i>	30152.49 ***	2.61	7.536	1.38
<i>F-value (probability)</i>	16.75 (0.000)		116.85 (0.0679)	
<i>Number of obs</i>	25		5	
<i>R²</i>	0.815		0.997	
* <i>p-value < 0.01; **p-value < 0.05; ***p-value < 0.10</i>				
^a <i>Dependent variable in logarithmic form.</i>				
^b <i>Omitted because no indicators are observed within this soil type.</i>				

€The independent variable is a discrete indicator with a limited range (1 to 10). Squaring it adds no meaningful information and may cause multicollinearity, making the quadratic term both redundant and difficult to interpret.

As shown in Table 4, the two indicators used to measure cultural ecosystem services (i.e.: "aesthetic landscape index" for the cultural service of aesthetics and "employment generation" for the service of information for cognitive development), exhibit similar pattern. Both indicators have a positive impact on the estimated economic value. Only in the case of the cultural service of aesthetics, the land use affects the estimated value. Specifically, for agricultural and forest soils, the economic value is lower compared to urban soils. This clearly reflects the high perceived economic value associated with interventions such as the creation or restoration of gardens and green spaces in urban areas, which enhance aesthetics.

Finally, Table 6 provides the economic value for the remaining indicators, where the direct benefit transfer method was applied

Table 6: Economic value of ecosystem services using benefit transfer method

	Indicator (units)	Type of soil	Economic value in €/ha (units or value)	Method	Source
Ecosystem service					
Regulating	Climate regulation				
	Total ecosystem organic content TCE (Tn/ha)	Forest	0.161	Market price	Hansen and Malmaeus (2016)
	Nutrient cycling				
Regulating	Available macronutrients (P, K, Ca, Mg, S) (Kg/ha)	Forest	0.329 (N) 0.474 (P) 0.459 (K)	Market price	Alam et al. (2013)
	Habitat for organism				
Supporting	Presence of natural green elements (%)	Urban	61.36 (1%)	Replacement Cost	Johnson and Geisendor (2019)
	Heritage				
Cultural	Presence of cultural elements (Yes/No)	Agri.	75.01	Benefit transfer	Alcon et al. (2022)
	Recreation				
	Recreation index (1-17)	Forest	558.96 (index value =4)	Choice experiment	Tyrväinene, L et al. (2014)
	Visitors and accommodations (n°/ha)	Forest	3.320 (each visitor)	Meta-analysis	Zandersen and Tol (2009)
			15.542 (each visitor)	Contingent Valuation	Silverio et al. (2021)
		Urban	4.971 (each visitor)	Avoided Cost	De Valck et al. (2019)

Next, we use meta-regression analysis to estimate the non-market economic value of the ecosystem services associated with each case study (LL and LH). To this end, for each case study, a baseline scenario is selected, specifically the scenario exhibiting the lowest soil health, and is compared with different scenarios (*Action*) using different interventions aidmen to enhance soil health. The selection of these scenarios, associated with the less and the most soil health provision, and the specific measurement units for the selected indicators were directly informed by the stakeholders and expert groups detailed in Table 1.

5.2.1. LH1. Mediterranean Forestry Soil: Restoration of soil by rotational grazing managing in woody pastures.

	Ecosystem service	Baseline (LH2.2)		Action (LH2.1)		Δ €/ha
		Indicator value	Estimated €/ha	Indicator value	Estimated €/ha	
Provisioning	Food					
	<i>Croop yield (Kg/ha)</i>	<i>na</i>	<i>na</i>	<i>na</i>	<i>na</i>	
	Fiber, energy or raw materials					
	<i>Plant biomass (Kg/ha)</i>	42	0.02	54	0.02	0.01
Regulating	Climate Regulation					
	<i>CO2 Sequestration (Tn/ha)</i>	91	1,529.571	100	1,641.51	111.94
	<i>Soil CO2 emissions (Tn/ha)</i>	48.00	-947.38	32.00	-699.28	248.10
	Water/air purification					
	<i>Pollution of surface or groundwater by nitrates (Mg/L/Ha)</i>	<i>na</i>	<i>na</i>	<i>na</i>	<i>na</i>	
	Nutrient recycling (Available macronutrients (Kg/ha))					
	<i>Nitrogen</i>	1.2	0.40	1.5	0.49	0.10
	<i>Phosphorus</i>	190	90.06	132	62.57	-27.49
	<i>Potassium</i>	103.41	47.47	100.94	46.33	-1.14
	Flood regulation and water storage					
	<i>Soil water retention capacity (m³/ha)</i>	419.00	62,908	507.00	64,241.83	1,333.79
	Erosion control					
	<i>Soil erosion rate (Tn/ha)</i>	<i>na</i>	<i>na</i>	<i>Na</i>	<i>na</i>	
<i>Bare soil (%)</i>	64.00	9.15	70.00	6.85	-2.30	
Supporting	Habitat for organism					
	<i>Presence of natural green elements (%)</i>	36.00	2,208.96	30.00	1,840.80	-368.16
Cultural	Heritage					
	<i>Presence of cultural elements (Yes/No)</i>	1.00	75.01	1.00	75.01	0.00
	Recreation					
	<i>Recreation Index (1-10)</i>	3.00	419.22	4.00	558.96	139.74

	Visitors and accommodations (n°)	30.00	282.93	30.00	282.93	0.00
	Aesthetics					
	Aesthetics landscape index (1-10)	2.00	7,763.55	10.00	20,008.59	12,245.04
	Information for cognitive development					
	Employment generation (AWU/ha)	1.00	5,726.38	2.00	11,452.76	5,726.38

5.2.2. LH2. Mediterranean Industrial Soil: Restoration of contaminated soil by metallic mining activities using artificial soils (Technosols).

Ecosystem service		Baseline (LH2.2)		Action (LH2.1)		Δ €/ha
		Indicator value	Estimated €/ha	Indicator value	Estimated €/ha	
Provisioning	Food					
	Croop yield (Kg/ha)	na	na	na	na	
	Fiber, energy or raw materials					
	Plant biomass (Kg/ha)	0.00	0.00	23,800	10.23	10.23
Regulating	Climate Regulation					
	CO ₂ Sequestration (Tn/ha)	15.00	124.25	54.00	324.27	200.02
	Soil CO ₂ emissions (Tn/ha)	16.00	-130.40	55.00	-328.76	-198.36
	Water/air purification					
	Pollution of surface or groundwater by nitrates (Mg/L/Ha)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Nutrient recycling (Available macronutrients (Kg/ha))					
	Nitrogen	0.01	0.00	0.49	0.16	0.16
	Phosphorus	0.00	0.00	34.50	16.35	16.35
	Potassium	12.11	5.56	102.38	46.99	41.43
	Flood regulation and water storage					
	Soil water retention capacity (m ³ /ha)	300.00	230.71	313.00	231.42	0.72
Erosion control						
Soil erosion rate (Tn/ha)	na	na	na	na		
Bare soil (%)	100.00	27.73	38.00	44.10	16.37	
Supporting	Habitat for organism					
	Presence of natural green elements (%)	0.00	0.00	62.00	3,804.32	3,804.32
Cultural	Heritage					
	Presence of cultural elements (Yes/No)	1.00	75.01	1.00	75.01	0.00
	Recreation					
	Recreation Index (1-10)	3.00	419.22	4.00	558.96	139.74
	Visitors and accommodations (n°)	2,043.00	19,267.67	4,717.00	44,486.34	25,218.67
Aesthetics						
Aesthetics landscape index (1-10)	10.00	20,008.59	8.00	16,947.33	-3,061.26	

Information for cognitive development					
Employment generation (AWU/ha)	0.00	0.00	0.15	865.26	865.26

5.2.3. LH3. Atlantic Industrial Soil: Restoration of contaminated soil by copper mining activities using artificial soils (Technosols).

	Ecosystem service	Baseline (LH3.2)		Action (LH3.1)		Δ €/ha
		Indicator value	Estimated €/ha	Indicator value	Estimated €/ha	
Provisioning	Food					
	Croop yield (Kg/ha)	na	na	na	na	
	Fiber, energy or raw materials					
	Plant biomass (Kg/ha)	0.00	0.00	550,000	236.50	263.50
Regulating	Climate Regulation					
	CO2 Sequestration (Tn/ha)	17.00	467.50	609.00	6,818.61	6,351.11
	Soil CO2 emissions (Tn/ha)	25.00	-423.54	209.00	-353.17	-2463.89
	Water/air purification					
	Pollution of surface or groundwater by nitrates (Mg/L/Ha)	0.00	3.92	10.00	-14.14	-18.06
	Nutrient recycling (Available macronutrients (Kg/ha))					
	Nitrogen	0.05	0.02	13.00	4.28	4.26
	Phosphorus	27.00	12.80	3,232.00	1,531.97	1,519.17
	Potassium	182.00	83.54	1,035.00	475.07	391.53
	Flood regulation and water storage					
	Soil water retention capacity (m ³ /ha)	417.00	201,030.49	829.00	221,698.05	20,667.56
	Erosion control					
Soil erosion rate (Tn/ha)	na	na	na	na		
Bare soil (%)	87.00	12.05	19.00	95.28	83.23	
Supporting	Habitat for organism					
	Presence of natural green elements (%)	35.00	2,147.60	80.00	4,908.80	2,761.20
Cultural	Heritage					
	Presence of cultural elements (Yes/No)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Recreation					
	Recreation Index (1-10)	2.00	279.48	5.00	698.70	419.22
	Visitors and accommodations (n ^o)	80.00	754.49	80.00	754.49	0.00
	Aesthetics					
	Aesthetics landscape index (1-10)	4.00	10,824.81	6.00	13,886.07	3,061.26
Information for cognitive development						
Employment generation (AWU/ha)	0.00	0.00	0.9	5,153.74	5,153.74	

5.2.4. LH4. Continental Urban Soil: Carbon sequestration and flood mitigation capacity of agricultural and forest uses in urban soils

5.2.4.1 LH4.1 Mulching, low soil disturbance, permanent grass cover, appropriate fertilisation (LH4.5: baseline)

	Ecosystem service	Baseline (LH4.5)		Action (LH4.1)		Δ €/ha
		Indicator value	Estimated €/ha	Indicator value	Estimated €/ha	
Provisioning	Food					
	Croop yield (Kg/ha)	na	na	na	na	
	Fiber, energy or raw materials					
	Plant biomass (Kg/ha)	na	na	na	na	
Regulating	Climate Regulation					
	CO ₂ Sequestration (Tn/ha)	214.00	128.89	341.00	183.85	54.95
	Soil CO ₂ emissions (Tn/ha)	49.51	-42.24	71.97	-56.17	-13.93
	Water/air purification					
	Pollution of surface or groundwater by nitrates (Mg/L/Ha)	0.00	23.63	0.00	23.63	0.00
	Nutrient recycling (Available macronutrients (Kg/ha))					
	Nitrogen	6.14	2.02	7.76	2.55	0.53
	Phosphorus	125.00	59.25	107.00	50.72	-8.53
	Potassium	266.00	122.09	477.00	218.94	96.85
	Flood regulation and water storage					
	Soil water retention capacity (m ³ /ha)	1,217.00	15.91	1,220.00	15.92	0.01
	Erosion control					
	Soil erosion rate (Tn/ha)	na	na	na	na	
Bare soil (%)	80.00	7.81	20.00	92.05	84.24	
Supporting	Habitat for organism					
	Presence of natural green elements (%)	25.00	1,534.00	80.00	4,908.80	3,374.80
Cultural	Heritage					
	Presence of cultural elements (Yes/No)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Recreation					
	Recreation Index (1-10)	1.00	139.74	1.00	139.74	0.00
	Visitors and accommodations (n°)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Aesthetics					
	Aesthetics landscape index (1-10)	2.00	7,947.35	6.00	14,069.87	6,122.52
Information for cognitive development						
Employment generation (AWU/ha)	2.00	11,452.76	0.07	383.67	-11,069.09	

5.2.4.2 LH4.2 Mulching, no soil disturbance, permanent vegetation cover (LH4.5: baseline)

	Ecosystem service	Baseline (LH4.5)		Action (LH4.2)		Δ €/ha
		Indicator value	Estimated €/ha	Indicator value	Estimated €/ha	
Provisioning	Food					
	Croop yield (Kg/ha)	na	na	na	na	
	Fiber, energy or raw materials					
	Plant biomass (Kg/ha)	na	na	29,980	0.00	
Regulating	Climate Regulation					
	CO2 Sequestration (Tn/ha)	214.00	128.89	371.00	196.05	67.16
	Soil CO2 emissions (Tn/ha)	49.51	-45.24	84.56	-63.51	-21.28
	Water/air purification					
	Pollution of surface or groundwater by nitrates (Mg/L/Ha)	0.00	23.63	0.00	23.63	0.00
	Nutrient recycling (Available macronutrients (Kg/ha))					
	Nitrogen	6.14	2.02	9.49	3.12	1.10
	Phosphorus	125.00	59.25	136.00	64.46	5.21
	Potassium	266.00	122.09	355.00	162.95	40.85
	Flood regulation and water storage					
	Soil water retention capacity (m ³ /ha)	1,217.00	15.91	1,139.00	15.62	-0.29
	Erosion control					
	Soil erosion rate (Tn/ha)	na	na	na	na	
Bare soil (%)	80.00	7.81	31.00	60.44	52.63	
Supporting	Habitat for organism					
	Presence of natural green elements (%)	25.00	1,534.00	69.00	4,233.84	2699.84
Cultural	Heritage					
	Presence of cultural elements (Yes/No)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Recreation					
	Recreation Index (1-10)	1.00	139.74	5.00	698.70	558.96
	Visitors and accommodations (n°)	0.00	0.00	80.00	754.49	754.49
	Aesthetics					
	Aesthetics landscape index (1-10)	2.00	7,947.35	2.00	7,947.35	0.00
Information for cognitive development						
Employment generation (AWU/ha)	2.00	11,452.76	0.01	76.16	-11,376.60	

5.2.4.3 LH4.3 No soil disturbance, no mineral fertilization, natural decay of trees and leaves (LH4.5: baseline)

	Ecosystem service	Baseline (LH4.5)		Action (LH4.3)		Δ €/ha
		Indicator value	Estimated €/ha	Indicator value	Estimated €/ha	
Provisioning	Food					
	Croop yield (Kg/ha)	na	na	na	na	
	Fiber, energy or raw materials					
	Plant biomass (Kg/ha)	na	na	na	na	
Regulating	Climate Regulation					
	CO2 Sequestration (Tn/ha)	214.00	128.89	296.00	165.05	36.15
	Soil CO2 emissions (Tn/ha)	49.51	-45.24	41.64	-23.10	5.22
	Water/air purification					
	Pollution of surface or groundwater by nitrates (Mg/L/Ha)	0.00	23.63	0.00	23.63	0.00
	Nutrient recycling (Available macronutrients (Kg/ha))					
	Nitrogen	6.14	2.02	6.19	2.04	0.02
	Phosphorus	125.00	59.25	136.00	64.46	5.21
	Potassium	266.00	122.09	131.00	60.13	-61.97
	Flood regulation and water storage					
	Soil water retention capacity (m ³ /ha)	1,217.00	15.91	1,043.00	15.28	-0.64
	Erosion control					
	Soil erosion rate (Tn/ha)	na	na	na	na	
Bare soil (%)	80.00	7.81	28.00	68.34	60.53	
Supporting	Habitat for organism					
	Presence of natural green elements (%)	25.00	1,534.00	72.00	4,417.92	2,883.92
Cultural	Heritage					
	Presence of cultural elements (Yes/No)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Recreation					
	Recreation Index (1-10)	1.00	139.74	2.00	279.48	139.74
	Visitors and accommodations (n°)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Aesthetics					
	Aesthetics landscape index (1-10)	2.00	7,947.35	8.00	17,131.13	9,183.78
Information for cognitive development						
Employment generation (AWU/ha)	2.00	11,452.76	0.07	383.67	-11,069.09	

5.2.4.3 LH4.4 Afforested area after abandoned agricultural land. No soil disturbance (LH4.5: baseline)

	Ecosystem service	Baseline (LH4.5)		Action (LH4.4)		Δ €/ha
		Indicator value	Estimated €/ha	Indicator value	Estimated €/ha	
Provisioning	Food					
	Croop yield (Kg/ha)	na	na	na	na	
	Fiber, energy or raw materials					
	Plant biomass (Kg/ha)	na	na	na	na	
Regulating	Climate Regulation					
	CO2 Sequestration (Tn/ha)	214.00	128.89	294.00	808.74	679.84
	Soil CO2 emissions (Tn/ha)	49.51	-42.24	61.90	-5963.45	-5921.21
	Water/air purification					
	Pollution of surface or groundwater by nitrates (Mg/L/Ha)	0.00	23.63	0.00	23.63	0.00
	Nutrient recycling (Available macronutrients (Kg/ha))					
	Nitrogen	6.14	2.02	8.08	2.66	0.64
	Phosphorus	125.00	59.25	74.00	35.08	-24.17
	Potassium	266.00	122.09	226.00	103.73	-18.36
	Flood regulation and water storage					
	Soil water retention capacity (m ³ /ha)	1,217.00	15.91	1,176.00	15.76	-0.15
	Erosion control					
	Soil erosion rate (Tn/ha)	na	na	na	na	
Bare soil (%)	80.00	7.81	22.00	85.76	77.95	
Supporting	Habitat for organism					
	Presence of natural green elements (%)	25.00	1,534.00	78.00	4,786.08	3,252.08
Cultural	Heritage					
	Presence of cultural elements (Yes/No)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Recreation					
	Recreation Index (1-10)	1.00	139.74	2.00	279.48	139.74
	Visitors and accommodations (n°)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Aesthetics					
	Aesthetics landscape index (1-10)	2.00	7,947.35	8.00	16,947.33	8,999.98
Information for cognitive development						
Employment generation (AWU/ha)	2.00	11,452.76	0.00	0.00	-11,452.76	

5.2.5. LH5. Boreal Urban Soil: Impact of urban agriculture on soil health.

5.2.5.1 LH5.1 Cucumber, tomato, onion, pumpkins and strawberries. Compost addition, mulching, no tillage, no agrochemicals use (LH5.4: baseline).

	Ecosystem service	Baseline (LH5.4)		Action (LH5.1)		Δ €/ha
		Indicator value	Estimated €/ha	Indicator value	Estimated €/ha	
Provisioning	Food					
	Crop yield (Kg/ha)	na	na	na	na	
	Fiber, energy or raw materials					
Regulating	Plant biomass (Kg/ha)	na	na	na	na	
	Climate Regulation					
	CO ₂ Sequestration (Tn/ha)	210.00	305.19	633.00	668.91	363.72
	Soil CO ₂ emissions (Tn/ha)	60.40	-125.80	77.54	-150.26	-24.46
	Water/air purification					
	Pollution of surface or groundwater by nitrates (Mg/L/Ha)	0.00	-110.01	9.00	-126.26	-16.25
	Nutrient recycling (Available macronutrients (Kg/ha))					
	Nitrogen	2.86	0.94	12.88	4.24	3.30
	Phosphorus	67.00	31.76	288.00	136.51	104.75
	Potassium	121.00	55.54	322.00	147.80	92.26
	Flood regulation and water storage					
	Soil water retention capacity (m ³ /ha)	305.00	0.98	798.00	1.11	0.12
	Erosion control					
	Soil erosion rate (Tn/ha)	na	na	na	na	
	Bare soil (%)	28.00	68.34	34.00	53.07	-15.26
Supporting	Habitat for organism					
	Presence of natural green elements (%)	72.00	4,417.92	66.00	4,049.76	-368.16
Cultural	Heritage					
	Presence of cultural elements (Yes/No)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Recreation					
	Recreation Index (1-10)	2.00	279.48	0.00	0.00	-279.48
	Visitors and accommodations (n ^o)	1,850.00	9,195.68	# ¹		
	Aesthetics					
	Aesthetics landscape index (1-10)	8.00	42,397.53	4.00	36,275.01	-6,122.52
Information for cognitive development						
Employment generation (AWU/ha)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	

¹ Data not applicable the case study LH5.1 involves a private company, and therefore, visitor access is restricted

5.2.5.2 LH5.2 *Quercus robur* forest with reduced grass management (LH5.4: baseline).

	Ecosystem service	Baseline (LH5.4)		Action (LH5.2)		Δ €/ha
		Indicator value	Estimated €/ha	Indicator value	Estimated €/ha	
Provisioning	Food					
	Croop yield (Kg/ha)	na	na	na	na	
	Fiber, energy or raw materials					
	Plant biomass (Kg/ha)	na	na	na	na	
Regulating	Climate Regulation					
	CO ₂ Sequestration (Tn/ha)	210.00	305.19	298.00	391.45	86.26
	Soil CO ₂ emissions (Tn/ha)	60.40	-125.80	67.40	-136.00	-10.20
	Water/air purification					
	Pollution of surface or groundwater by nitrates (Mg/L/Ha)	0.00	-110.01	0.00	-110.01	0.00
	Nutrient recycling (Available macronutrients (Kg/ha))					
	Nitrogen	2.86	0.94	5.26	1.73	0.79
	Phosphorus	67.00	31.76	45.00	21.33	-10.43
	Potassium	121.00	55.54	109.00	50.03	-5.51
	Flood regulation and water storage					
	Soil water retention capacity (m ³ /ha)	305.00	0.98	614.00	1.06	0.08
	Erosion control					
	Soil erosion rate (Tn/ha)	na	na	na	na	
Bare soil (%)	28.00	68.34	19.00	95.28	26.95	
Supporting	Habitat for organism					
	Presence of natural green elements (%)	72.00	4,417.92	81.00	4,970.16	552.24
Cultural	Heritage					
	Presence of cultural elements (Yes/No)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Recreation					
	Recreation Index (1-10)	2.00	279.48	5.00	698.70	419.22
	Visitors and accommodations (n°)	1,850.00	9,195.68	2,200.00	10,935.41	1,739.72
	Aesthetics					
	Aesthetics landscape index (1-10)	8.00	42,397.53	6.00	39,336.27	-3,061.26
Information for cognitive development						
Employment generation (AWU/ha)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	

5.2.5.3 LH5.3 *Leotodum taraxacoides* with reduced grass management, addition of compost and no agrochemicals use (LH5.4: baseline).

	Ecosystem service	Baseline (LH5.4)		Action (LH5.3)		Δ €/ha
		Indicator value	Estimated €/ha	Indicator value	Estimated €/ha	
Provisioning	Food					
	Croop yield (Kg/ha)	na	na	na	na	
	Fiber, energy or raw materials					
	Plant biomass (Kg/ha)	na	na	na	na	
Regulating	Climate Regulation					
	CO ₂ Sequestration (Tn/ha)	210.00	305.19	415.00	495.41	190.22
	Soil CO ₂ emissions (Tn/ha)	60.40	-125.80	85.11	-160.55	-34.75
	Water/air purification					
	Pollution of surface or groundwater by nitrates (Mg/L/Ha)	0.00	-110.01	0.00	-110.01	0.00
	Nutrient recycling (Available macronutrients (Kg/ha))					
	Nitrogen	2.86	0.94	8.41	2.77	1.83
	Phosphorus	67.00	31.76	158.00	74.89	43.13
	Potassium	121.00	55.54	195.00	89.51	33.97
	Flood regulation and water storage					
	Soil water retention capacity (m ³ /ha)	305.00	0.98	784.00	1.10	0.12
	Erosion control					
	Soil erosion rate (Tn/ha)	na	na	na	na	
Bare soil (%)	28.00	68.34	29.00	65.64	-2.69	
Supporting	Habitat for organism					
	Presence of natural green elements (%)	72.00	4,417.92	71.00	4,356.56	-61.36
Cultural	Heritage					
	Presence of cultural elements (Yes/No)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Recreation					
	Recreation Index (1-10)	2.00	279.48	0.00	0.00	-279.48
	Visitors and accommodations (n ^o)	1,850.00	9,195.68	# ¹	#	
	Aesthetics					
Aesthetics landscape index (1-10)	8.00	42,397.53	4.00	36,275.01	-6,122.52	
Information for cognitive development						
Employment generation (AWU/ha)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	

¹Data not applicable the case study LH5.3 involves a private company, and therefore, visitor access is restricted

5.2.6. LH6. Boreal Forestry Soil: Effects planting strategies, fertilization, and sustainable soil management on soil health.

	Ecosystem service	Baseline (LH6.1)		Action (LH6.2)		Δ €/ha
		Indicator value	Estimated €/ha	Indicator value	Estimated €/ha	
Provisioning	Food					
	Croop yield (Kg/ha)	na	na	na	na	
	Fiber, energy or raw materials					
Regulating	Plant biomass (Kg/ha)	na	na	na	na	
	Climate Regulation					
	CO2 Sequestration (Tn/ha)	24.00	43.69	113.00	139.42	95.72
	Soil CO2 emissions (Tn/ha)	25.00	-45.05	40.00	-449.83	-404.78
	Water/air purification					
	Pollution of surface or groundwater by nitrates (Mg/L/Ha)	0.00	-248.22	0.00	-248.22	0.00
	Nutrient recycling (Available macronutrients (Kg/ha))					
	Nitrogen	0.18	0.06	0.87	0.29	0.23
	Phosphorus	8.00	3.79	85.00	40.29	36.50
	Potassium	64.00	29.38	61.00	28.00	-1.38
	Flood regulation and water storage					
	Soil water retention capacity (m ³ /ha)	139.00	0.07	215.00	0.08	0.00
	Erosion control					
	Soil erosion rate (Tn/ha)	na	na	na	na	
	Bare soil (%)	39.00	42.00	25.00	76.78	34.78
Supporting	Habitat for organism					
	Presence of natural green elements (%)	61.00	3,742.96	75.00	4,602.00	859.04
Cultural	Heritage					
	Presence of cultural elements (Yes/No)	na	na	na	na	
	Recreation					
	Recreation Index (1-10)	na	na	na	na	
	Visitors and accommodations (n ^o)	na	na	na	na	
	Aesthetics					
	Aesthetics landscape index (1-10)	na	na	na	na	
Information for cognitive development						
Employment generation (AWU/ha)	na	na	na	na		

5.2.7. LH7. Atlantic Agricultural Soil: Sustainable practices (crop diversification, minimum tillage, fertilization reduction...) around the inclusion of a new crop in the area: lupines.

	Ecosystem service	Baseline (LH7.2)		Action (LH7.1)		Δ €/ha
		Indicator value	Estimated €/ha	Indicator value	Estimated €/ha	
Provisioning	Food					
	Croop yield (Kg/ha)	na	na	na	na	
	Fiber, energy or raw materials					
	Plant biomass (Kg/ha)	na	na	na	na	
Regulating	Climate Regulation					
	CO ₂ Sequestration (Tn/ha)	217.00	45.96	217.00	45.96	9.40
	Soil CO ₂ emissions (Tn/ha)	49.00	-14.78	67.00	-18.76	-3.98
	Water/air purification					
	Pollution of surface or groundwater by nitrates (Mg/L/Ha)	3.00	-253.64	5.00	-257.25	-3.61
	Nutrient recycling (Available macronutrients (Kg/ha))					
	Nitrogen	6.79	2.23	8.57	2.82	0.59
	Phosphorus	223.00	105.70	218.00	103.33	-2.37
	Potassium	1,040.00	477.36	649.00	297.89	-179.47
	Flood regulation and water storage					
	Soil water retention capacity (m ³ /ha)	790.00	0.09	858.00	0.09	0.00
	Erosion control					
	Soil erosion rate (Tn/ha)	na	na	na	na	
Bare soil (%)	18.00	98.58	14.00	112.35	13.78	
Supporting	Habitat for organism					
	Presence of natural green elements (%)	82.00	5,031.52	86.00	5,276.96	245.44
Cultural	Heritage					
	Presence of cultural elements (Yes/No)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Recreation					
	Recreation Index (1-10)	1.00	139.74	1.00	139.74	0.00
	Visitors and accommodations (n°)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Aesthetics					
	Aesthetics landscape index (1-10)	6.00	14,069.87	6.00	14,069.87	0.00
Information for cognitive development						
Employment generation (AWU/ha)	2.00	11,452.76	3.00	17,179.14	5,726.38	

5.2.8. LL1. Mediterranean Agricultural Soil: Application of conservation agriculture practices, as potential climate change adaptation and mitigation strategies: effects on soil health and crop production.

5.2.8.1. LL1.8: Experimental site SS7: sod seeding (soft wheat /maize wholemeal shredded) (LL1.5 (CT3): baseline).

	Ecosystem service	Baseline (LL1.5)		Action (LL1.8)		Δ €/ha
		Indicator value	Estimated €/ha	Indicator value	Estimated €/ha	
Provisioning	Food					
	Croop yield (Kg/ha)	na	na	na	na	
	Fiber, energy or raw materials					
	Plant biomass (Kg/ha)	na	na	na	na	
Regulating	Climate Regulation					
	CO ₂ Sequestration (Tn/ha)	124.00	258.79	151.00	300.72	41.93
	Soil CO ₂ emissions (Tn/ha)	15.33	-52.60	27.32	-81.70	-29.10
	Water/air purification					
	Pollution of surface or groundwater by nitrates (Mg/L/Ha)	0.00	161.83	0.00	161.83	0.00
	Nutrient recycling (Available macronutrients (Kg/ha))					
	Nitrogen	4.12	1.36	1.71	0.56	-0.79
	Phosphorus	59.60	28.25	227.60	107.88	79.63
	Potassium	575.00	263.93	794.00	364.45	100.52
	Flood regulation and water storage					
	Soil water retention capacity (m ³ /ha)	841.00	6,567.63	513.00	6,075.99	-491.65
	Erosion control					
	Soil erosion rate (Tn/ha)	na	na	na	na	
Bare soil (%)	79.00	7.44	30.00	63.01	55.57	
Supporting	Habitat for organism					
	Presence of natural green elements (%)	21.00	1,288.56	70.00	4,295.20	3006.64
Cultural	Heritage					
	Presence of cultural elements (Yes/No)	1.00	75.01	1.00	75.01	0.00
	Recreation					
	Recreation Index (1-10)	7.00	978.18	7.00	978.18	0.00
	Visitors and accommodations (n°)	1012.00	9,544.24	782.00	7,375.09	-2169.15
	Aesthetics					
	Aesthetics landscape index (1-10)	10.00	20,192.39	10.00	20,192.39	0.00
Information for cognitive development						
Employment generation (AWU/ha)	na	na	na	na	0.00	

**5.2.8.1. LL1.11: Experimental site SS7: sod seeding (soft wheat /maize wholemeal shredded)
(LL1.5 (CT3): baseline).**

	Ecosystem service	Baseline (LL1.5)		Action (LL1.11)		Δ €/ha
		Indicator value	Estimated €/ha	Indicator value	Estimated €/ha	
Provisioning	Food					
	Croop yield (Kg/ha)	na	na	na	na	
	Fiber, energy or raw materials					
	Plant biomass (Kg/ha)	na	na	na	na	
Regulating	Climate Regulation					
	CO2 Sequestration (Tn/ha)	124.00	258.79	652.00	916.98	658.19
	Soil CO2 emissions (Tn/ha)	15.33	-52.60	37.54	-104.09	-51.50
	Water/air purification					
	Pollution of surface or groundwater by nitrates (Mg/L/Ha)	0.00	161.83	0.00	161.83	0.00
	Nutrient recycling (Available macronutrients (Kg/ha))					
	Nitrogen	4.12	1.36	0.56	0.18	-1.17
	Phosphorus	59.60	28.25	15.40	7.30	-20.95
	Potassium	575.00	263.93	204.00	93.64	-170.29
	Flood regulation and water storage					
	Soil water retention capacity (m ³ /ha)	841.00	6567.63	563.00	6148.72	-418.91
	Erosion control					
	Soil erosion rate (Tn/ha)	na	na	na	na	
Bare soil (%)	79.00	7.44	55.00	16.66	9.22	
Supporting	Habitat for organism					
	Presence of natural green elements (%)	21.00	1,288.56	45.00	2,761.20	1472.64
Cultural	Heritage					
	Presence of cultural elements (Yes/No)	1.00	75.01	1.00	75.01	0.00
	Recreation					
	Recreation Index (1-10)	7.00	978.18	7.00	978.18	0.00
	Visitors and accommodations (n ^o)	1,012.00	9,544.24	na	na	
	Aesthetics					
	Aesthetics landscape index (1-10)	10.00	20,192.39	na	na	
Information for cognitive development						
Employment generation (AWU/ha)	na	na	na	na		

5.2.9. LL2. Continental Agricultural Soil: Adoption of sustainable management to enhance C sequestration and soil health.

	Ecosystem service	Baseline (LL2.4)		Action (LL2.2)		Δ €/ha
		Indicator value	Estimated €/ha	Indicator value	Estimated €/ha	
Provisioning	Food					
	Croop yield (Kg/ha)	na	na	na	na	
	Fiber, energy or raw materials					
	Plant biomass (Kg/ha)	na	na	na	na	
Regulating	Climate Regulation					
	CO2 Sequestration (Tn/ha)	413.00	186.77	850.00	323.77	137.00
	Soil CO2 emissions (Tn/ha)	61.44	-43.71	54.67	-39.99	3.72
	Water/air purification					
	Pollution of surface or groundwater by nitrates (Mg/L/Ha)	0.00	38.74	0.00	38.74	0.00
	Nutrient recycling (Available macronutrients (Kg/ha))					
	Nitrogen	0.86	0.28	0.95	0.31	0.03
	Phosphorus	239.00	113.29	256.00	121.34	8.06
	Potassium	492.00	225.83	401.00	184.06	-41.77
	Flood regulation and water storage					
	Soil water retention capacity (m ³ /ha)	1,067.00	6.58	892.00	6.31	-0.27
	Erosion control					
	Soil erosion rate (Tn/ha)	na	na	na	na	
Bare soil (%)	53.00	18.99	47.00	27.41	8.42	
Supporting	Habitat for organism					
	Presence of natural green elements (%)	48.00	2,945.28	56.00	3,436.16	490.88
Cultural	Heritage					
	Presence of cultural elements (Yes/No)	1.00	75.01	1.00	75.01	0.00
	Recreation					
	Recreation Index (1-10)	2.00	279.48	2.00	279.48	0.00
	Visitors and accommodations (n ^o)	200.00	1,886.21	200.00	1,886.21	0.00
	Aesthetics					
	Aesthetics landscape index (1-10)	0.00	4,886.09	0.00	4,886.09	0.00
Information for cognitive development						
Employment generation (AWU/ha)	1.50	8,589.57	1.50	8,589.57	0.00	

6. Quantifying the total economic value (Market and Non-Market) of ecosystem services associated with soil management scenarios in LHs and LLs.

This section presents a quantitative assessment of the total economic value of ecosystem services derived from soil management scenarios (interventions) in LHs and LLs. To provide a comprehensive overview of the interventions' impact, the analysis integrates both market and non-market benefits with the environmental impact costs associated with each specific practices carried out in each intervention. Environmental costs are associated with the impact of the practices, valuing the associated impact estimated by using a Life Cycle Assessment method. Economic value of the environmental impact comes from the project's internal "Report on Environmental Cost-Benefit Analysis of the Soil Management Practices," (included as Annex 2) ensuring cross-methodological consistency within the project framework.

By comparing the pre- and post-intervention status of these ecosystems and their associated economic values, the aim is to quantify the increase in economic benefits resulting from these interventions.

To ensure methodological consistency, investment costs are expressed as annual equivalent costs (AEC) following standard accounting practices. This annualization reflects the long-term nature of the interventions, assuming a project lifetime of 68 years, and applies a discount rate of 3.5%. This approach allows investment costs to be properly aligned with the annual flow of ecosystem service benefits.. Furthermore, to address the inherent variability of these estimations, an uncertainty factor has been incorporated by introducing confident intervals. These intervals originate from the uncertainty generated during the meta-regression analysis for non-market value predictions. To aggregate these individual ranges into a single *Total Benefit* interval, we employed the Quadratic Summation of Uncertainties (Root Sum Square - RSS). Under this approach, the lower and upper bounds of the total value are not merely a simple sum of extremes. Instead, while the midpoints (central values) are summed algebraically to preserve the impact of negative inputs (such as costs or environmental disservices) the uncertainty margins are combined using the square root of the sum of squares. This ensures that the final reported interval follows standard error propagation protocols, providing a realistic measure of the cumulative uncertainty derived from our statistical predictions.

It should be noted that the presence of certain predicted values outside the aggregate bounds stem from the high volatility and restricted observation count in specific sites. Consequently, the calculated intervals serve as a representative statistical benchmark, acknowledging the stochastic nature of the underlying data while providing a robust framework for assessing the economic return on investment in soil restoration.

6.1. LH1. Mediterranean Forestry Soil: Restoration of soil by rotational grazing managing in woody pastures.

		Economic Value (€/ha)			Uncertainty	
		Baseline (LH12)	Action (LH11)	Δ €/ha	Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Market	Revenue	0.00	175.00	175.00	175.00	175.00
	Cost	180.00	253.00	73.00	73.00	73.00
	Investment					
	O&M	180.00	253.00	73.00		
	Margin	-180.00	-78.00	102.00	102.00	102.00
Non-market	Ecosystem services					
	Provisioning	0.02	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.51
	Regulating	63,637.30	65,300.30	1,663.00	574.55	3964.96
	Supporting	2,208.96	1,840.80	-368.16	-368.16	-368.16
	Cultural	14,267.09	32,378.25	18,111.16	10633.85	26468.07
	Total Ecosystem services	80,113.37	99,519.37	19,406.00	12356.25	28549.37
Practices environmental impact cost		0.00	395.04	395.04	395.04	395.04
Total benefit		79,933.37	99,046.33	19,112.96	12,063.20	28,256.33

6.2. LH2. Mediterranean Industrial Soil: Restoration of contaminated soil by metallic mining activities using artificial soils (Technosols).

		Economic Value (€/ha)			Uncertainty	
		Baseline (LH22)	Action (LH21)	Δ €/ha	Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Market	Revenue	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Cost	0.00	1,496.27	1,496.27	1,496.27	1,496.27
	Investment	0.00	1,496.27	1,496.27		
	O&M	0.00	0.00	0.00		
	Margin	0.00	-1,496.27	-1,496.27	-1,496.27	-1,496.27
Non-market	Ecosystem services					
	Provisioning	0.00	10.23	10.23	0.00	12199.69
	Regulating	257.84	334.54	76.70	54.39	247.16
	Supporting	0.00	3,804.32	3,804.32	3804.32	3804.32
	Cultural	39,770.49	62,932.90	23,162.41	21338.48	25095.31
	Total Ecosystem services	40,028.33	67,081.99	27,053.66	26888.59	39655.07
Practices environmental impact cost		0.00	2.92	2.92	2.92	2.92
Total benefit		40,028.33	65,582.80	25,554.46	25,389.39	38,155.88

6.3. LH3. Atlantic Industrial Soil: Restoration of contaminated soil by copper mining activities using artificial soils (Technosols).

		Economic Value (€/ha)			Uncertainty	
		Baseline (LH32)	Action (LH31)	Δ €/ha	Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Market	Revenue	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Cost	0.00	1,908.68	1,908.68	1,908.68	1,908.68
	Investment	0.00	1,908.68	1,908.68		
	O&M	0.00	0.00	0.00		
	Margin	0.00	-1,908.68	-1,908.68	-1,908.68	-1,908.68
Non-	Ecosystem services					
	Provisioning	0.00	236.50	236.50	0.00	28192.55
	Regulating	200,986.27	227,548.18	26,561.91	13121.23	63645.56

	<i>Supporting</i>	2,147.60	4,908.80	2,761.20	2761.20	2761.20
	<i>Cultural</i>	11,858.78	20,493.00	8,634.22	6368.45	11652.84
	<i>Total Ecosystem services</i>	214,992.64	253,186.48	38,193.84	35202.20	93300.84
	<i>Practices environmental impact cost</i>	0.00	75.16	75.16	75.16	75.16
	Total benefit	214,992.64	251,202.64	36,210.00	33,218.36	91,317.00

6.4. LH4. Continental Urban Soil: Carbon sequestration and flood mitigation capacity of agricultural and forest uses in urban soils.

6.4.1 LH4.1 Mulching, low soil disturbance, permanent grass cover, appropriate fertilisation (LH4.5: baseline)

		Economic Value (€/ha)			Uncertainty	
		Baseline (LH4.5)	Action (LH4.1)	Δ €/ha	Lower Bound	Upper Bound
<i>Market</i>	Revenue	857.00	11,130.00	10,273.00	10,273.00	10,273.00
	Cost	1,353.00	6,416.00	5,063.00	5,063.00	5,063.00
	<i>Investment O&M</i>	0.00	0.00	0.00		
	Margin	-496.00	4,714.00	5,210.00	5,210.00	5,210.00
<i>Non-market</i>	Ecosystem services					
	Provisioning	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Regulating	317.38	531.50	214.12	3109.83	15498.63
	Supporting	1,534.00	4,908.80	3,374.80	3374.80	3374.80
	Cultural	19,539.85	14,593.28	-4,946.57	-11144.14	-304.07
	<i>Total Ecosystem services</i>	21,391.23	20,033.57	-1,357.65	-1275.95	15185.80
	<i>Practices environmental impact</i>	481.18	612.67	131.49	131.49	131.49
	Total benefit	20,414.05	24,134.90	3,720.86	3,802.56	20,264.31

6.4.2 LH4.2 Mulching, no soil disturbance, permanent vegetation cover (LH4.5: baseline)

		Economic Value (€/ha)			Uncertainty	
		Baseline (LH4.5)	Action (LH4.2)	Δ €/ha	Lower Bound	Upper Bound

Market	Revenue	857.00	na	0.00	0.00	
	Cost	1,353.00	na	0.00	0.00	
	<i>Investment</i>	0.00				
	<i>O&M</i>	1,353.00				
	<i>Margin</i>	-496.00		0.00	0.00	
Non-market	Ecosystem services					
	Provisioning	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
	Regulating	317.38	462.76	145.38	3307.49	18122.21
	Supporting	1,534.00	4,233.84	2,699.84	2699.84	2699.84
	Cultural	19,539.85	9,476.70	-10,063.15	-12903.80	-8851.44
	<i>Total Ecosystem services</i>	21,391.23	14,173.30	-7,217.93	-5142.41	10216.55
<i>Practices environmental impact cost</i>		481.18	na			
Total benefit		20,414.05	14,173.30	-7,217.93	-5,142.41	10,216.55

6.4.3 LH4.3 No soil disturbance, no mineral fertilization, natural decay of trees and leaves (LH4.5: baseline)

		Economic Value (€/ha)		Uncertainty		
		Baseline (LH4.5)	Action (LH4.3)	Δ €/ha	Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Market	Revenue	857.00	na		0.00	0.00
	Cost	1,353.00	na		0.00	0.00
	<i>Investment</i>	0.00				
	<i>O&M</i>	1,353.00				
	<i>Margin</i>	-496.00			0.00	0.00
Non-market	Ecosystem services					
	Provisioning	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Regulating	317.38	361.91	44.53	1933.63	13426.81
	Supporting	1,534.00	4,417.92	2,883.92	2883.92	2883.92
	Cultural	19,539.85	17,794.28	-1,745.57	-9659.99	4628.70
	<i>Total Ecosystem services</i>	20,895.23	22,574.11	1,182.88	-1120.20	17217.18
<i>Practices environmental impact cost</i>		481.18	na			
Total benefit		19,918.05	22,574.11	1,182.88	-1,120.20	17,217.18

6.4.4 LH4.4 Afforested area after abandoned agricultural land. No soil disturbance (LH4.5: baseline)

		Economic Value (€/ha)		Uncertainty		
		Baseline (LH4.5)	Action (LH4.4)	Δ €/ha	Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Market	Revenue	857.00	na		0.00	0.00
	Cost	1,353.00	na		0.00	0.00
	Investment	0.00				
	O&M	1,353.00				
	Margin	-496.00			0.00	0.00
Non-market	Ecosystem services					
	Provisioning	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Regulating	317.38	-4,888.09	-5,205.46	1766.41	9974.03
	Supporting	1,534.00	4,786.08	3,252.08	3252.08	3252.08
	Cultural	19,539.85	17,226.81	-2,313.04	-10139.45	4285.89
	Total Ecosystem services	21,391.23	17,124.80	-4,266.42	-2102.91	14493.95
Practices environmental impact		na	na			
Total benefit		20,895.23	17,124.80	-4,266.42	-2,102.91	14,493.95

6.5. LH5. Boreal Urban Soil: Impact of urban agriculture on soil heath.

6.5.1 LH5.1 Cucumber, tomato, onion, pumpkins and strawberries. Compost addition, mulching, no tillage, no agrochemicals use (LH5.4: baseline).

		Economic Value (€/ha)		Uncertainty		
		Baseline (LH5.4)	Action (LH5.1)	Δ €/ha	Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Market	Revenue	0.00	334.93	334.93	334.93	334.93
	Cost	173.44	198.51	25.07	25.07	25.07
	Investment	173.44	0.00	-173.44		
	O&M	0.00	198.51	198.51		
	Margin	-173.44	136.42	309.86	309.86	309.86
Non-market	Ecosystem services					
	Provisioning	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

	<i>Regulating</i>	226.94	735.12	508.18	11252.05	61887.60
	<i>Supporting</i>	4,417.92	4,049.76	-368.16	-368.16	-368.16
	<i>Cultural</i>	42,677.01	36,275.01	-6,402.00	-9865.54	-2968.30
	<i>Total Ecosystem services</i>	47,321.87	41,059.89	-6,261.98	1018.35	58551.14
<i>Practices environmental impact cost</i>		0.00	7.66	7.66	7.66	7.66
Total benefit		47,148.43	41,188.65	-5,959.78	1,320.55	58,853.34

6.5.2 LH5.2 Quercus robur forest with reduced grass management (LH5.4: baseline).

		Economic Value (€/ha)		Uncertainty		
		Baseline (LH5.4)	Action (LH5.2)	Δ €/ha	Lower Bound	Upper Bound
<i>Market</i>	Revenue	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Cost	173.44	173.44	0.00	0.00	0.00
	<i>Investment</i>	173.44	173.44	0.00		
	<i>O&M</i>	0.00	0.00	0.00		
	Margin	-173.44	-173.44	0.00	0.00	0.00
<i>Non-market</i>	<i>Ecosystem services</i>					
	Provisioning	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	<i>Regulating</i>	226.94	314.87	87.93	1901.93	13002.47
	<i>Supporting</i>	4,417.92	4,970.16	552.24	552.24	552.24
	<i>Cultural</i>	51,872.69	50,970.38	-902.32	-2634.09	814.53
	<i>Total Ecosystem services</i>	56,517.56	56,255.41	-262.15	1282.72	12906.62
<i>Practices environmental impact cost</i>		na	na			
Total benefit		56,344.11	56,081.97	-262.15	1,282.72	12,906.62

6.5.3 LH5.3 Leotodum taraxacoides with reduced grass management, addition of compost and no agrochemicals use (LH5.4: baseline).

		Economic Value (€/ha)		Uncertainty		
		Baseline (LH5.4)	Action (LH5.3)	Δ €/ha	Lower Bound	Upper Bound

Market	Revenue	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Cost	173.44	173.44	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Investment	173.44	173.44	0.00		
	O&M	0.00	0.00	0.00		
	Margin	-173.44	-173.44	0.00	0.00	0.00
Non-market	Ecosystem services					
	Provisioning	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Regulating	226.94	458.76	231.82	4644.93	28322.83
	Supporting	4,417.92	4,356.56	-61.36	-61.36	-61.36
	Cultural	42,677.01	36,275.01	-	-9865.54	-2968.30
	Total Ecosystem services	47,321.87	41,090.33	-	-2325.41	22336.61
Practices environmental impact cost		na	na			
Total benefit		47,148.43	40,916.89	-	-2,325.41	22,336.61
				6,231.54		

6.6. LH6. Boreal Forestry Soil: Effects planting strategies, fertilization, and sustainable soil management on soil health.

		Economic Value (€/ha)			Uncertainty	
		Baseline (LH61)	Action (LH62)	Δ €/ha	Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Market	Revenue	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Cost	0.00	132.66	132.66	132.66	132.66
	Investment	0.00	59.03	59.03		
	O&M	0.00	73.63	73.63		
	Margin	0.00	-132.66	-132.66	-132.66	-132.66
Non-market	Ecosystem services					
	Provisioning	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Regulating	-174.28	-413.21	-238.94	-62841.56	-12083.07
	Supporting	3,742.96	4,602.00	859.04	859.04	859.04
	Cultural	na	na		0.00	0.00
	Total Ecosystem services	3,568.68	4,188.79	620.10	-61982.52	-11224.03

<i>Practices environmental impact cost</i>	0.00	19.72	19.72	19.72	19.72
Total benefit	3,568.68	4,036.41	467.73	-62,134.90	-11,376.41

6.7. LH7. Atlantic Agricultural Soil: Sustainable practices (crop diversification, minimum tillage, fertilization reduction...) around the inclusion of a new crop in the area: lupines.

		Economic Value (€/ha)			Uncertainty	
		Baseline (LH72)	Action (LH71)	Δ €/ha	Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Market	Revenue	2,413.00	3,210.00	797.00	797.00	797.00
	Cost	2,306.00	1,681.00	-625.00	-625.00	-625.00
	<i>Investment</i>	0.00	0.00	0.00		
	<i>O&M</i>	2,306.00	1,681.00	-625.00		
	Margin	107.00	1,529.00	1,422.00	1,422.00	1,422.00
Non-market	Ecosystem services					
	Provisioning	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Regulating	461.49	295.82	-165.67	931.32	6280.30
	Supporting	5,031.52	5,276.96	245.44	245.44	245.44
	Cultural	25,662.37	31,388.75	5,726.38	5116.47	7156.21
	Total Ecosystem services	31,155.38	36,961.53	5,806.15	7125.24	12849.94
<i>Practices environmental impact cost</i>	596.84	400.47	-196.37	-196.37	-196.37	
Total benefit	30,665.54	38,090.06	7,424.52	8,743.61	14,468.31	

6.8. LL1. Mediterranean Agricultural Soil: Application of conservation agriculture practices, as potential climate change adaptation and mitigation strategies: effects on soil health and crop production.

6.8.1. LL1.8: Experimental site SS7: sod seeding (soft wheat /maize wholemeal shredded) (LL1.5(CT3): baseline).

	Economic Value (€/ha)	Δ €/ha	Uncertainty
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		Baseline (LL1.5)	Action (LH1.8)		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Market	Revenue	1,443.71	12,379.50	10,935.79	10,935.79	10,935.79
	Cost	182.00	285.00	103.00	103.00	103.00
	Investment O&M	0.00 182.00	0.00 285.00	0.00 103.00		
	Margin	1,261.71	12,094.50	10,832.79	10,832.79	10,832.79
Non-market	Ecosystem services					
	Provisioning	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Regulating	7,236.62	6,992.73	-243.90	-545.90	2850.34
	Supporting	1,288.56	4,295.20	3,006.64	3006.64	3006.64
	Cultural	30,789.82	28,620.67	-2,169.15	-2169.15	-2169.15
	Total Ecosystem services	39,315.00	39,908.60	593.60	291.59	3687.84
Practices environmental impact cost		273.36	199.72	-73.64	-73.64	-73.64
Total benefit		40,303.35	51,803.38	11,500.03	11,198.02	14,594.27

6.8.2. LL1.11: Experimental site SS7: sod seeding (soft wheat /maize wholemeal shredded) (LL1.5 (CT3): baseline).

		Economic Value (€/ha)			Uncertainty	
		Baseline (LL1.5)	Action (LH1.11)	Δ €/ha	Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Market	Revenue	1,443.71	4,658.13	3,214.42	3,214.42	3,214.42
	Cost	182.00	2,124.00	1,942.00	1,942.00	1,942.00
	Investment O&M	0.00 182.00	0.00 2,124.00	0.00 1,942.00		
	Margin	1,261.71	2,534.13	1,272.42	1,272.42	1,272.42
	Ecosystem services					
Non-market	Provisioning	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Regulating	7,236.62	7,241.22	4.59	13530.76	74720.78
	Supporting	1,288.56	2,761.20	1,472.64	1472.64	1472.64
	Cultural	1,053.19	1,053.19	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Total Ecosystem services	9,578.37	11,055.61	1,477.23	15003.40	76193.42
	Practices environmental impact cost		273.36			
Total benefit		10,566.72	13,589.74	2,749.65	16,275.82	77,465.84

6.9. LL2. Continental Agricultural Soil: Adoption of sustainable management to enhance C sequestration and soil health

		Economic Value (€/ha)			Uncertainty	
		Baseline (LL2.4)	Action (LL2.2)	Δ €/ha	Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Market	Revenue	478.54	3,945.40	3,466.86	3,466.86	3,466.86
	Cost	829.11	6,869.13	6,040.02	6,040.02	6,040.02
	Investment			0.00		
	O&M	829.11	6,869.13	6,040.02		
	Margin	-350.57	-2,923.73	-2,573.16	-2,573.16	-2,573.16
Non-market	Ecosystem services					
	Provisioning	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Regulating	546.76	661.95	115.20	12251.90	65597.41
	Supporting	2,945.28	3,432.16	486.88	490.88	490.88
	Cultural	15,716.36	15,716.36	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Total Ecosystem services	19,208.40	19,810.48	602.08	12742.78	66088.29
Practices environmental impact cost		378.50	634.82	256.32	256.32	256.32
Total benefit		18,479.34	16,251.93	-2,227.40	9,913.30	63,258.81
<p>*Note: The baseline and action scenarios are defined using grouped averages. Specifically, mean values were calculated for the biodynamic management scenarios (Scenarios 1–15) and for the mineral fertilization scenarios (Scenarios 16–24). The comparison therefore reflects average outcomes for mineral fertilization (baseline) versus biodynamic management (action), rather than individual scenario values.</p>						

7. Discussion (Total economic value of soil ecosystem services in LHs and LLs)

The total economic value, comprising market components (investment and O&M costs and revenues), non-markets components (the estimated economic value of ecosystem services and disservices provided by soil, such as provisioning, regulating, supporting and cultural) and the environmental impact cost derived from the interventions, varied across different soils interventions in various case studies (LHs and LLs). By comparing baseline conditions with different actions across different land uses in terms of the total economic value, we gain insights into the economic returns on ecosystem soil restoration and its broader benefits for human well-being and environmental conservation.

Regarding forest land use, the LH1 intervention involves a transition from forest, with the absence of livestock, to rotational grazing with the introduction of livestock. Although this action results in a negative market margin (–€78/ha), it is still more favourable than the initial situation, where the margin was –€180/ha. Furthermore, while the intervention introduces an environmental impact cost of €395.04/ha, the substantial increases in cultural and regulating services contribute an additional non-market benefit of €18,111.16/ha and 1663.00€/ha respectively, yielding a total benefit of €19,112.96 per hectare.

Similarly, LH6 supports an action that shifts from unsustainable to more sustainable forest management. Although the action entails evident market-related costs (investment and operation) and environmental impact cost, substantial improvements are observed in non-market ecosystem services, particularly regulating and supporting services. Overall, the transition results in an increase in total economic value (€467.73 per hectare), indicating that ecosystem service gains more than offset the incurred cost.

Regarding reclaimed tailing ponds (LH2) and mining land use (LH3), the results show that the restoration of an abandoned mining area into a forest through the application of technosols (LH2) results in a negative market margin (–€1,496.27 per hectare). Nonetheless, significant enhancements in provision of ecosystem services, especially in cultural and supporting services (non-market value) yield a total benefit of €25,554.46 per hectare. Also, the restoration of an actively exploited mining soil into a forest using technosols designed to mitigate contamination hazards (LH3) incurs notable market costs; however, the action produces a considerable increase in non-market value, especially in regulating and cultural services, resulting in a net total benefit increase of €36,210.00 per hectare.

Management scenarios in agricultural and urban land uses soils are associated with several actions presented in LH4, LH5, LH7, LL1 and LL2. LH4 encompasses several interventions in agricultural soils transitioning toward sustainable uses. For example, LH4.1 (mulching, low soil disturbance, and permanent grass cover) enhances market margins, whereas variations observed in LH4.2 (Mulching, no soil disturbance, permanent vegetation cover) to LH4.4 (Afforested area after abandoned agricultural land. No soil disturbance) illustrate that the selection of specific practices is critical to maximizing non-market benefits. Some interventions display reductions in cultural or regulating services, indicating the need for careful strategy design.

LH5 shows negative economic results in the three actions implemented, agricultural soils in an urban context. Some net gains are present in regulating and supporting services from certain interventions, although these do not offset the negative impacts on cultural services. In LH7, the introduction of alternative crops (lupines) accompanied by sustainable practices results in a robust increase in both market margins and cultural ecosystem services, underscoring the economic viability of integrating sustainable practices within agricultural settings.

Finally, the cases of LL1 and LL2 (Mediterranean and continental agricultural soils, respectively) demonstrate that adopting conservation agriculture practices and biodynamic systems can enhance market value and overall margins, as shown in LL1.8 and L1.11. Gains in non-market value across ecosystem services are most notable in LL1.11 and LL2.2. However, some management scenarios, such as LL1.8, exhibit a decrease in the non-market value of cultural and regulating services,

suggesting that the balance between restoration objectives and climate adaptation measures must be carefully managed.

In conclusion, the integration of environmental impact costs alongside market and non-market values provides a more rigorous net benefit perspective. The interventions in mining land use face challenges in terms of investment and operational costs; however, conversion to forest ecosystems significantly amplifies non-market benefits, particularly in cultural and regulating services. In agricultural land uses, the adoption of soil sustainable management practices can effectively restructure cost-benefit dynamics, leading to improvements in both market and non-market values. Urban uses present complex interactions between economic and ecological benefits. While some interventions enhance ecosystem services, others may lead to trade-offs. Finally, forest land uses illustrate that long-term ecological gain, such as enhanced carbon sequestration or biodiversity, may offset the lower short-term economic returns.

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Annex 1 – Description of the lighthouses and living labs used in InBestSoil

LIGHTHOUSE #1: Restoration of soil by rotational grazing managing in woody pastures

PEDOCLIMATIC REGION: MEDITERRANEAN
LAND USE: AGRICULTURAL
COUNTRY: SPAIN
LOCATION: TALAVÁN (EXTREMADURA)
MEAN ANNUAL TEMPERATURE: 16,7 °C
MEAN ANNUAL PRECIPITATION: 644 MM
SOIL TYPE (WORLD REFERENCE BASE): CAMBISOLS,
LUVISOLS, ACRISOLS

LIGHTHOUSE #1: Restoration of soil by rotational grazing managing in woody pastures

- LEARNING AND DEMONSTRATION FARM
- COLLABORATIVE SPACE
- TESTED REGENERATIVE GRAZING
- ORGANIC PRODUCTION
- MONITORING OF PASTURES AND BIODIVERSITY
- 232 HA OF PASTURE
- AUTOCHTHONOUS BREEDS OF CATTLE AND SHEEP
- IMPROVED PRODUCTION AND MARKETING

DEHESA EL BALDÍO

Personas innovando por una ganadería generadora de naturaleza
Alianzas para un planeta sano

DEHESA RENTABLE

- Arbolado de Futuro → Gestión Forestal
- Pazas autóctonas productivas con valor añadido → Mejora productiva y de la comercialización
- Suelos y pastos vivos → Línea clave
- Talento → Pastores rotacional
- Punto de encuentro → Formación, difusión y sensibilización
- Alianzas, difusión y sensibilización

Esta propuesta afronta el reto de convertir la dehesa en un agroecosistema sostenible mediante el desarrollo e implementación de buenas prácticas de manejo, acreditables mediante la marca de calidad Go-DEHESA, que permite la diferenciación de los productos por sus atributos de restauración ambiental y social, a lo que se suma la rentabilidad de explotaciones agropecuarias de titularidad pública o privada, en dehesas comunales o de grupo.

GoDEHESA

Pastoreo racional como herramienta de regeneración

El Pastoreo Racional es un práctica de gestión del pastoreo que mitiga el crecimiento de los grandes robales de especies invasoras, genera un agrosistema más resiliente, se fortalece el suelo y se evita, según se permita, reducir la erosión.

Ventajas del pastoreo racional

- Menor riesgo de incendios
- Mayor y selectiva calidad del pasto
- Cede del agua y nutrientes más eficaces
- Mayor regeneración natural del arbolado
- Mayor de la fertilidad y capacidad de carbono en el suelo
- Mayor de la salud de las animales

LIGHTHOUSE #1: Soil health threats

- Low below and aboveground biodiversity
- Erosion
- Overgrazing
- Low soil quality
- Low soil organic matter content
- Landscape simplification

LIGHTHOUSE #1: REPRESENTATIVE OF HIGH SOIL HEALTH

- Extension: 5,94 ha,
- Geographical coordinates: 39.71294, -6.25808
- Year of establishment: 2019
- Current vegetation type / cropping system (to choose between both): Dehesa
- Main vegetation species / crops (to choose between both): leguminous plants and Gramineae, and trees typically of the *Quercus* genus (holm oaks) which are in good condition, together with a high presence of a shrub layer composed mainly of rockroses, genista, broom and lavender.
- Sustainable management practices performed that permitted high soil health:
 - Rotational grazing
 - Non sowing and tillage
 - High intensity grazing + Short time of grazing + Enough resting time
 - Autochthonous breeds: Blanca cacereña
- Main economic activities: cow meat production
- Actors involved: CICYTEX, Fundación Entretantos

REPRESENTATIVE OF HIGH SOIL HEALTH

NEARBY CONTROL AREA WITH LOW SOIL HEALTH

- Extension: 18,1 ha
- Geographical coordinates: 39.71634, -6.26137
- Year of establishment of current management: 1993
- Current vegetation type / cropping system (to choose between both): Dehesa
- Main vegetation species / crops (to choose between both): leguminous plants and Gramineae, and trees typically of the *Quercus* genus (holm oaks) which are in good condition, together with a high presence of a shrub layer composed mainly of rockroses, genista, broom and lavender.
- Management practices performed that led to low soil health:
 - Reforestation
 - Continuous tillage over years
 - Lack of livestock
- Main economic activities: cow meat production

NEARBY CONTROL AREA WITH LOW SOIL HEALTH

LIGHTHOUSE #2: Restoration of contaminated soil – Cartagena, Spain

PEDOCLIMATIC REGION: MEDITERRANEAN

LAND USE: INDUSTRIAL – FORMER METALLIC MINE

COUNTRY: SPAIN

LOCATION: CARTAGENA

GEOGRAPHICAL COORDINATES: 37.594005, -0.886302

MEAN ANNUAL TEMPERATURE: 17 °C

MEAN ANNUAL PRECIPITATION: 280 MM

SOIL TYPE (WORLD REFERENCE BASE): TECHNOSOLS

LIGHTHOUSE #2: Soil health threats

- Soil and water pollution
- Hyperacidification
- Hypersulfation
- Low/null nutrients and organic matter contents
- Metallic (Cd, Cu, Pb, Zn) contamination
- Non-metallic (As) contamination
- Secondary Salinization
- Null vegetation cover

LIGHTHOUSE #2: REPRESENTATIVE OF HIGH SOIL HEALTH

Santa Antonieta Mine (remediated in 2012)

- **Extension/Location:** 1 ha/coordinates: 37.5994005,-0.886302
- Year of establishment: 2012
- **Current vegetation type:** Mediterranean shrubland
- **Main vegetation species:** *Piptaterum miliaceum*, *Salvia Rosmarinus*, *Pistacia lentiscus*, *Dittrichia viscosa*, *Hyparrhenia hirta*
- The **remediation project consisted of** the creation of artificial soils (Technosols) applying the aided phytostabilization technique based on the combination of heavy metal-tolerant plants (phytostabilisation) and organic or inorganic amendments (chemical stabilisation), aims to reduce soil metal bioavailability while improving soil health.
- **Main economic activities:** tourism as guided tours to mines.
- **Actors involved:**
 - Portman Golf SL. Owner of the land (private)
 - Regional Government of Murcia (public)
 - ANSE. Ecologist NGO
 - Fundación Sierra Minera. Private foundation for the protection of the former mining district
 - Regional and local governments

LIGHTHOUSE #2: REPRESENTATIVE OF HIGH SOIL HEALTH

Santa Antonieta Mine

NEARBY CONTROL AREA WITH LOW SOIL HEALTH

San Francisco Javier Mine (non remediated)

- Extension/ Location: 5 ha / coordinates: 37.593997, -0.881523
- Year of establishment of current management: tailings abandoned since 1950's up to 1970's
- Current vegetation type: none
- Main vegetation species: none
- Management practices performed that led to low soil health: metallic mining (mostly Pb, Zn and Fe)

NEARBY CONTROL AREA WITH LOW SOIL HEALTH

LIGHTHOUSE #3: Restoration of contaminated soil – Touro, Spain

PEDOCLIMATIC REGION: ATLANTIC
LAND USE: INDUSTRIAL – COPPER MINING
COUNTRY: SPAIN
LOCATION: TOURO (GALICIA)
GEOGRAPHICAL COORDINATES: 42.879, -8.321
MEAN ANNUAL TEMPERATURE: 12.7 °C
MEAN ANNUAL PRECIPITATION: 1242 MM
SOIL TYPE (WORLD REFERENCE BASE): TECHNOSOLS

LIGHTHOUSE #3: Soil health threats

- Soil and water pollution
 - Hyperacidification
 - Hyperoxidation with Fe⁺³
 - Hypersulfation
 - Hyperaluminization
 - Metallic contamination (Mn, Cu, Zn, Ni)
- Extremophile Ecosystems
- Bio-catalysis acceleration caused by oxygen-reduction reaction.

LIGHTHOUSE #3: REPRESENTATIVE OF HIGH SOIL HEALTH

- Extension/ Location: 30 ha, coordinates: 42.878, -8.321
- Year of establishment: 1999
- Current vegetation type: Atlantic
- Main vegetation species: Autochthonous herbaceous and shrubby plants
- The remediation project consisted in the production of artificial soils (Technosols), specifically designed to counter-act the hazardous properties of soil contamination caused by mining activities.
 - Technosol #1: Eutrophic Andic Soil
 - Technosol #2: sambaqui
- Main economic activities: Production of aggregates for construction
- Actors involved:
 - CVAN – Centro de Valorización Ambiental del Norte
 - Francisco Gómez Cia (Land Owner)
 - Explotaciones Gallegas (Previous land owner)
 - TEN – Tratamientos Ecológicos del Noroeste

LIGHTHOUSE #3: REPRESENTATIVE OF HIGH SOIL HEALTH

NEARBY CONTROL AREA WITH LOW SOIL HEALTH

- Extension/ Location: 15 ha, coordinates 42.877, -8.319
- Year of establishment of current management: 1999
- Current vegetation type: No vegetation
- Management practices performed that led to low soil health:
 - Copper Mining
 - Aggregates production
- Main economic activities: Production of aggregates for construction

NEARBY CONTROL AREA WITH LOW SOIL HEALTH

LIGHTHOUSE #4: Urban soils

PEDOCLIMATIC REGION: TEMPERATE CONTINENTAL
LAND USE: AGRICULTURAL, FOREST
COUNTRY: CROATIA
LOCATION: ZAGREB
MEAN ANNUAL TEMPERATURE: 6,2 – 11,4 °C
MEAN ANNUAL PRECIPITATION: 859,4 MM
SOIL TYPE (WORLD REFERENCE BASE): STAGNOSOLS

LIGHTHOUSE #4: Soil health threats

- Overexploitation
- Low biodiversity
- Structural deterioration
- Low soil quality
- Soil compaction
- Low soil organic matter content
- Soil abandonment
- Flood risk

LIGHTHOUSE #4: REPRESENTATIVE OF HIGH SOIL HEALTH (1)

- **Extension:** 1 ha
- **Geographical coordinates:** N 45.85, E 16.17
- **Year of establishment:** 2007.
- **Current vegetation type:** apple orchard
- **Main vegetation species:** apple orchard
- Sustainable management practices performed that permitted high soil health:
 - Mulching
 - Low soil disturbance
 - Permanent grass cover
 - Appropriate fertilisation
- **Main economic activities:** apple production
- **Actors involved:** The area is under the supervision of the Faculty of Agriculture

LIGHTHOUSE #4: REPRESENTATIVE OF HIGH SOIL HEALTH (2)

- **Extension:** 1 ha
- **Geographical coordinates:** N 45.85, E 16.17
- **Year of establishment:** 1996.
- **Current vegetation type:** Grassland
- **Main vegetation species:** grass-clover mixtures
- **Sustainable management practices performed that permitted high soil health:**
 - Mulching
 - No soil disturbance
 - Permanent vegetation cover
- **Main economic activities:** no economic value
- **Actors involved:** The area is under the supervision of the Faculty of Agriculture

LIGHTHOUSE #4: REPRESENTATIVE OF HIGH SOIL HEALTH (3)

- **Extension:** 50 ha
- **Geographical coordinates:** N 45.85, E 16.18
- **Year of establishment:** >200 years
- **Current vegetation type:** Forest
- **Main vegetation species:** *Quercus petraea* - *Robinia pseudoacacia*
- **Sustainable management practices performed that permitted high soil health:**
 - No soil disturbance
 - No mineral fertilization
 - Natural decay of trees and leaves
- **Main economic activities:** wood stock
- **Actors involved:** area is under supervision of Faculty of Forestry

LIGHTHOUSE #4: REPRESENTATIVE OF HIGH SOIL HEALTH (4)

- **Extension:** 1 ha
- **Geographical coordinates:** N 45.85, E 16.17
- **Year of establishment:** 1991.
- **Current vegetation type:** secondary forest (afforested)- abandoned agricultural land
- **Main vegetation species:** Shrubbery
- **Sustainable management practices performed that permitted high soil health:**
 - No soil disturbance
- **Main economic activities:** no economic value
- **Actors involved:** not permitted

LIGHTHOUSE #4: REPRESENTATIVE OF HIGH SOIL HEALTH

NEARBY CONTROL AREA WITH LOW SOIL HEALTH

- **Extension:** 20 ha
- **Geographical coordinates:** N 45.85, E 16.18
- **Year of establishment of current management:** 2007.
- **Current vegetation type / cropping system:** annual cropland
- **Main vegetation species / crops:** winter wheat, winter barley, winter oats, soybean, maize
- **Management practices performed that led to low soil health:**
 - Conventional tillage
 - Intensive mineral fertilization
 - Lack of organic fertilization
 - Absence of cover cropping
 - Absence of mulching
- **Main economic activities:** certified seed production (wheat, soybean)

NEARBY CONTROL AREA WITH LOW SOIL HEALTH

LIGHTHOUSE #5: Impact of urban agriculture on soil health

PEDOCLIMATIC REGION: BOREAL
LAND USE: AGRICULTURAL, GRASSLAND,
COUNTRY: LITHUANIA
LOCATION: VILNIUS
MEAN ANNUAL TEMPERATURE: 7.2 °C
MEAN ANNUAL PRECIPITATION: 764 MM
SOIL TYPE (WORLD REFERENCE BASE): *ANTROPOSOLS*

LIGHTHOUSE #5: Soil health threats

- Flood risk
- Soil erosion
- Soil compaction
- Soil pollution
- Reduced biodiversity
- Reduced organic matter

LIGHTHOUSE #5: REPRESENTATIVE OF HIGH SOIL HEALTH (Urban Garden)

- **Extension:** 0.17 ha
- **Geographical coordinates:** 54.7253296 N; 25.2785659 E
- **Year of establishment:** 1960
- **Current vegetation type:** Urban garden
- **Main vegetation species:** cucumber, tomato, onion, pumpkins and strawberries
- **Sustainable management practices performed that permitted high soil health:**
 - Composting;
 - Mulching;
 - No tillage
 - No agrochemicals use
- **Main economic activities:** vegetable production
- **Actors involved:** Small scale farmers

LIGHTHOUSE #5: REPRESENTATIVE OF HIGH SOIL HEALTH (Urban garden)

LIGHTHOUSE #5: REPRESENTATIVE OF HIGH SOIL HEALTH (Urban park)

- **Extension:** 1.19 ha
- **Geographical coordinates:** 54.7268095 N; 25.2760011 E
- **Year of establishment:** 1995
- **Current vegetation type:** Urban forest
- **Main vegetation species:** *Quercus robur* (L.)
- **Sustainable management practices performed that permitted high soil health:**
 - Reduced grass management
- **Main economic activities:** None
- **Actors involved:** Vilnius Municipality

NEARBY CONTROL AREA WITH LOW SOIL HEALTH (Urban park)

LIGHTHOUSE #5: REPRESENTATIVE OF HIGH SOIL HEALTH (Urban grassland)

- **Extension:** 0.09 ha
- **Geographical coordinates:** 54.7250879 N; 25.2783507 E
- **Year of establishment:** 1960
- **Current vegetation type:** Urban grassland
- **Main vegetation species:** *Leotodum taraxacoides*
- **Sustainable management practices performed that permitted high soil health:**
 - Reduced grass management
 - Composting
 - No agrochemicals use
- **Main economic activities:** None
- **Actors involved:** Small scale farmers

LIGHTHOUSE #5: REPRESENTATIVE OF HIGH SOIL HEALTH (Urban grassland)

NEARBY CONTROL AREA WITH LOW SOIL HEALTH (Lawn)

- **Extension:** 0.96 ha
- **Geographical coordinates:** 54.7270868 N; 25.2792543 E
- **Year of establishment:** 1995
- **Current vegetation type:** Lawn
- **Main vegetation species:** *Leotodum taraxacoides*
- **Sustainable management practices performed that permitted high soil health:**
 - Intensive grass management
- **Main economic activities:** None
- **Actors involved:** Vilnius Municipality

LIGHTHOUSE #6: Boreal forestry Soil

PEDOCLIMATIC REGION: BOREAL

LAND USE: FOREST (FOREST WITH TERRAIN, RECULTIVATED MINE, WITH WOOD ASH FERTILIZED FOREST)

COUNTRY: LATVIA

LOCATION: FOREST LANDSCAPE (REGION)

MEAN ANNUAL TEMPERATURE: +5.9 °C

MEAN ANNUAL PRECIPITATION: 700 MM

LIGHTHOUSE #6: REPRESENTATIVE OF HIGH SOIL HEALTH

- Extension: 9917 ha,
- Geographical coordinates: 57.330699, 25.950759
- Year of establishment: 1960 regional nature protection territory. As research territory since 1999. Since 2001 State forest research area.
- Current vegetation type - forest
- Pine, spruce, birch and other forest vegetation (EU habitats 6450,7160, 91E0, 9080)
- Sustainable management practices performed that permitted high soil health:
 - Balance of nutrient elements
 - Afforestation/ reforestation –promotion of forest vegetation formation
 - Tending /thinning - increase of soil radiation for species in vegetation cover
 - 'Gentle' soil preparation
- Main economic activities: Forestry, nature protection, education, science
- Actors involved: Forest research station, Ministry of Agriculture, University of life sciences and technologies.

LIGHTHOUSE #7: REPRESENTATIVE OF HIGH SOIL HEALTH

- Extension: 130 ha
- Year of establishment: 2005
- Soil type (World Reference Base): Fluvisol
- Mean annual temperature and precipitation: 10,6°C and 848 mm
- Location: 51.94129253, 5.69297944
- Current cropping system: biodynamic, regenerative
- Main crops: Onion, pumpkin, potato, grass-clover, lupin, peas, sugarmaize, wheat, rye
- Sustainable management practices performed that permitted high soil health and economic development:
 - Wide crop rotation
 - Organic farming
 - Reduced tillage
 - N-fixers
 - Green manures
- Main economic activities: Crop sales, projects, education, specialized hired labour
- Actors involved: WUR, Lekker Lupine, Agrifirm, Baltussen

Annex 2 – REPORT ON ENVIRONMENTAL COST-BENEFIT ANALYSIS OF THE SOIL MANAGEMENT PRACTICES

InBestSoil

Monetary valuation of soil ecosystem services and creation of initiatives to invest in soil health: setting a framework for the inclusion of soil health in business and in the policy making process- InBestSoil

REPORT ON ENVIRONMENTAL COST-BENEFIT ANALYSIS OF THE SOIL MANAGEMENT PRACTICES

Prepared by:

University of Vigo (UVIGO) – GEN Research Group
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Glossary of key terms

CBA (Cost-Benefit Analysis): An analytical tool used to support decision-making by comparing the benefits (increases in well-being) and costs (decreases in well-being) of different options in monetary terms. In this report, an environmental CBA (e-CBA) framework is applied to internalise environmental externalities within the economic balance.

Externalities: Environmental and social impacts (positive or negative) resulting from soil management that are not reflected in conventional market prices. In this report, negative externalities are quantified as environmental costs, while positive ones are considered as ecosystem services.

Internalisation of Externalities: The process of incorporating environmental costs and ecosystem service values into economic assessments to ensure these reflect the full social impact of interventions.

Cradle-to-gate approach: A Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) scope that covers the entire value chain, including raw material extraction, the production of external inputs (e.g., fertilizers, machinery), and transport to the site. It excludes use and end-of-life stages. This approach ensures that environmental costs include impacts occurring at a global scale, which often take place very far from the physical boundaries of the managed or restored area (upstream impacts).

Willingness to Pay (WTP): The maximum amount an individual is willing to pay to avoid a negative environmental impact or to secure an environmental benefit. It is the standard economic measure used to capture the social value of non-market goods and services.

Shadow Prices (Environmental Prices): Monetary values assigned to biophysical impacts that do not have a market price, such as pollutant emissions. They represent the loss of economic welfare for society for every extra unit of impact (e.g., 1 kg of CO₂) released into the environment.

Benefit Transfer: A valuation method that estimates the economic value of environmental impacts by adapting monetary estimates from a previous study (e.g., EU-27 average) to specific new case studies. Rigorous adjustments such as spatial (income-based) and temporal corrections (price inflation) are mandatory to ensure geographical relevance and methodological accuracy.

Purchasing Power Parity (PPP): An economic metric used to adjust GDP per capita for spatial differences in income levels between countries. It ensures that the benefit transfer approach for environmental prices is used according to the local economic context of each case study.

Income Elasticity (β): A coefficient reflecting how willingness to pay for environmental quality changes with income. A value of 0.65 is applied in this study, consistent with environmental valuation literature, to adjust environmental prices spatially and temporally.

Social Margin: The final indicator representing the net social balance of a practice. It is calculated as the sum of the Market Margin (Revenues minus Management Costs) and the Non-market Margin (Ecosystem Services minus Environmental Costs).

Trade-offs: Situations in which the improvement of one dimension of performance (e.g., profitability) results in deterioration of another (e.g., environmental quality). The e-CBA framework makes these trade-offs explicit by expressing all effects in monetary terms.

1. Executive Summary

Purpose

This report is based on the results of the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) integrated within the InBestSoil project, with a particular focus on identifying and quantifying the environmental impacts associated with the different soil management practices. The purpose of this environmental cost-benefit analysis (e-CBA) is to go beyond technical LCA by incorporating a monetary valuation of environmental impacts.

By monetising environmental externalities (calculating environmental costs), this report provides a single metric (€) to evaluate different soil management practices and guide decision-making in a circular bioeconomy context. This approach reveals "hidden" costs typically omitted from conventional economic assessments, enabling the integrated evaluation of environmental performance, economic viability, and social value of different soil management practices within a single analytical framework.

Intended audience

The document was designed for policymakers involved in land-use planning, soil protection, and environmental management at both national and EU levels. It is also relevant for researchers in environmental economics, soil science, sustainability assessment, and agroecology. In addition, the report provides evidence-based insights for land managers and practitioners responsible for agricultural, forestry, urban, or industrial soils who seek to optimize soil health and sustainability outcomes through informed management decisions.

Description of the main activities

The main activity was to integrate two different methodologies, LCA and e-CBA, to translate biophysical environmental impacts into monetary units. To do that, impact data derived from the standardised LCA (D3.3- *Report on LCA for activities developed in order to improve soil health in LHs*, WP3, InBestSoil), based on a functional unit of 1 hectare of managed soil, were monetised using a benefit transfer approach to estimate environmental costs. To do this, the Handbook of Environmental Prices (CE Delft, 2024) was applied, providing midpoint monetary valuation factors fully compatible with the ReCiPe 2016 impact assessment framework.

To ensure geographical and temporal relevance, spatial and temporal adjustments were applied. European average prices (EU-27) from the Handbook of Environmental Prices were adapted to the socioeconomic contexts of Spain, Croatia, Lithuania, Latvia, Italy, the Netherlands, and Switzerland, using GDP per capita in purchasing power parity (PPP). Next, the environmental prices were translated to national current prices, which enables environmental externalities to

be directly compared with the financial costs and benefits of soil management. In addition, a temporal adjustment updated 2021 reference prices to 2024 values, reflecting income growth and changes in the social valuation of environmental protection.

Key results

The integrated e-CBA approach provides a consistent basis to evaluate soil management practices across different soils uses:

- In **agricultural systems** (e.g., LH7), switching to organic and regenerative practices reduced environmental costs by 33%, while also improving financial performance. This demonstrates that sustainable farming can simultaneously lower environmental costs and increase overall socio-economic value.
- In **urban soils** (e.g., LH4), conventional cropland was found to be economically inefficient once its environmental cost was internalised. In contrast, sustainable practices such as grasslands reduced environmental costs by 91%, highlighting that some conventional practices that appear profitable may generate net losses for society.
- The restoration of **mining-contaminated industrial soils** (e.g., LH3) involves high environmental costs, reaching 5,110 €/ha, mainly due to the intensive material and transport requirements. These impacts represent one-time investment costs to remediate historical damage and are justified by the long-term recovery of soil functions and ecosystem services, resulting in a strongly positive Net Social Balance exceeding 25,000 €/ha per year.
- In Mediterranean **forests**, sustainable practices like regenerative grazing (e.g., LH1) were associated with higher environmental costs due to increased management intensity but also generated new economic activities (meat production) and improved soil fertility. This illustrates that higher environmental costs can reflect trade-offs associated with the creation of long-term social and economic benefits.
- Environmental costs accounted for between 20% and 60% of total soil management costs across several LLs/LHs, demonstrating that a substantial share of societal costs is typically omitted from conventional economic assessments.

Research and practice implications

The results demonstrate the importance of integrating economic valuation of environmental impacts into sustainability assessments to identify trade-offs between environmental performance and socio-economic value. Quantifying environmental costs is essential for a comprehensive evaluation of soil systems, yet these costs are rarely included in agricultural and land management studies. The LCA-eCBA framework applied in this project addresses this gap by monetising externalities associated with different soil management practices

using a cradle-to-gate approach, which captures impacts at a global scale, often occurring far from the managed area.

An additional outcome is the fact that this methodology (LCA–eCBA framework) proved to be an effective double-checking tool, allowing cross-validation of results and the detection of potential inconsistencies. This added robustness check increases the reliability of the results and provides researchers, advisors and practitioners with a practical tool to identify environmental “hotspots” and to design soil management systems that are economically viable while enhancing soil functions, biodiversity and long-term ecosystem resilience.

Policy implications

The findings show that decisions based solely on private profitability can be misleading. For instance, in urban contexts, conventional cropland becomes economically inefficient once environmental costs are internalised through e-CBA. In contrast, sustainable management practices such as apple orchards, despite having higher environmental costs, achieve a clearly positive economic balance because the high market value of production compensates for both environmental and management costs.

Overall, these results confirm that sustainable soil management can reduce environmental pressures and, when combined with economic and social benefits, can justify public intervention. Such evidence supports the integration of environmental cost–benefit analysis into land-use planning, urban soil management strategies and agri-environmental schemes at both national and EU levels, contributing directly to the Soil Mission objectives on soil health, climate mitigation, biodiversity enhancement and the reduction of land degradation. Policy interventions may be based in alternative instruments: regulations, economic incentives (taxes, subsidies), so agents internalise social cost and benefits in their decision-making, etc.

Conclusion

The integration of e-CBA within InBestSoil demonstrates that monetising environmental impacts substantially changes the interpretation of soil management performance and reveals costs that remain invisible in conventional assessments. This report provides a robust and transferable framework to evaluate soil management practices on a common monetary basis, supporting evidence-based decisions across agricultural, urban, forest, and industrial contexts. The results establish a methodological foundation for subsequent InBestSoil activities, particularly for upscaling sustainability assessments, refining LLs/LHs comparisons, and supporting the design of soil health investment and policy instruments that ensure a resilient and climate-neutral European bioeconomy.

2. Objectives

Develop an integrated
LCA-eCBA
methodological
framework

Monetize
environmental
impacts (e-costs)

Standardize
results into a
single metric (€)

Assess social
sustainability and
trade-offs

Identify and
promote
sustainable
practices

Support
evidence-based
policy and
planning

3. Methodology

3.1. FRAMEWORK OF THE ENVIRONMENTAL COST-BENEFIT ANALYSIS

Cost-benefit analysis (CBA) is an analytical tool used to support decision-making by comparing the benefits and costs of different options in monetary terms. The benefits are defined as an increase in well-being, while costs represent decreases in well-being (OECD, 2018). By monetising and aggregating these factors, CBA helps to determine whether a proposed measure represents a net gain for society. It is typically applied when evaluating policy measures to ensure efficient resource allocation. The aim is to capture the full range of consequences of a project or measure for all members of society (Boardman et al., 2018).

There are two types of CBA: (i) ex-ante, to decide whether to allocate resources to a particular project or policy, and (ii) ex-post, to assess efficiency at different stages after the project is completed. Regardless of the typology, the steps to develop a CBA are clear, systematic and iterative, and evolve as the project matures to optimise the analysis. Thus, the methodology of a conventional CBA includes the steps shown in Figure 1. However, when market prices are used without adjustment, results may be distorted, as market prices rarely reflect environmental and social values (Hoogmartens et al., 2014).

Figure 1. Main steps in conducting a conventional cost-benefit analysis (CBA)

While financial (also termed private) cost-benefit analysis typically focuses on investment, operating, and management costs that are directly expressed in monetary terms, this analysis requires the inclusion of environmental and social externalities, which may occur off-site and over longer time horizons, and are often overlooked in conventional economic assessments (Babí Almenar et al., 2023; Finnveden et al. 2009). This highlights the importance of combining biophysical impact assessment with monetary valuation to support informed decision-making (Babí Almenar et al., 2023).

As a result, CBA has evolved beyond its traditional focus on purely financial returns, incorporating environmental considerations into its analytical framework, in response to the increasing demand for sustainable decision-making. This led to the development of **environmental cost-benefit analysis (hereafter e-CBA)**, in which environmental externalities are explicitly included in the assessment. E-CBA refers to the application of cost-benefit analysis to projects or that affect the natural environment as a direct or indirect consequence of their implementation (OECD, 2018). So, e-CBA is the approach used in this study as it ensures the integration of environmental criteria into the decision-making process (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Schematic of the e-CBA. Source: OCDE 2018

Figure 3. Schematic framework illustrating the integration of LCA (environmental impacts) and e-CBA (environmental costs)

3.2. MONETARY VALUATION OF ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACTS

Economic assessment of environmental impact data derived from the LCA ensures that externalities are appropriately considered into decision-making. This approach goes beyond traditional LCA by assigning monetary values to environmental impacts, enabling a more comprehensive assessment of soil management interventions. The results support sustainable resource management and help policy makers to design more environmentally responsible land management strategies.

The analysis begins with the detailed LCA of each case study, which quantifies environmental impacts by tracking both inputs (e.g., energy, water) and outputs (e.g., emissions) (see deliverable D3.3 for details). In this report, we adopt the same **functional unit of 1 hectare of managed soil** as defined in the LCA ensuring consistency and compatibility between environmental and economic assessments. This approach enables a coherent comparison of impacts and performance across all soil management scenarios (see Figure 3)

Monetary valuation is the process of converting biophysical impact measurements into monetary units. It plays a key role in internalising externalities within economic systems, addressing market failures, and improving resource allocation (Pizzol et al., 2015). This is usually achieved by estimating the individual willingness to pay (WTP) to avoid negative impacts, or the willingness to accept (WTA) compensation for tolerating them. This helps to capture the social value of non-market goods and services, making environmental and social trade-offs more visible and actionable (Pearce and Barbier, 2000).

Several studies highlight the benefits of integrating monetary valuation into LCA, particularly during the weighting phase, where it allows aggregation of different impact categories into a single, interpretable metric (Ahlroth, 2014; Ahlroth et al., 2011; Finnveden et al., 2009; Amadei et al., 2021; Jeswani et al., 2010). Expressing environmental impacts in a common monetary unit facilitates direct comparison and supports evidence-based decision-making.

Approaches to monetary valuation

There are various methods for translating environmental impact categories from LCA into monetary values for inclusion in cost-benefit analyses (Amadei et al. 2021; Pizzol et al. 2015). Ideally, specific fieldwork using contingent valuation methods would be conducted to determine these values. However, due to time and budget constraints, this approach is not feasible within the InBestSoil project.

Instead, this report applies the **benefit transfer method**, which adjusts damage costs estimated in other contexts. This involves reviewing the economic literature and selecting studies that have analysed and monetised the environmental impacts identified in the LCA. The benefit transfer method uses monetary values of environmental goods from one context to estimate the value of similar goods in another, where their value is unknown (Navrud and Ready, 2007).

In the field of environmental economics, the method has been extensively tested, mainly in the US and Europe, with validations assessing the reliability of benefit transfer across locations and populations (Wilson and Hoehn, 2006; Boutwell and Westra, 2013).

For this study we have used the **Handbook of Environmental Prices developed by CE Delft (2024)**, which provides a practical and consistent approach. The environmental prices provided reflect the social cost of pollution, expressed in euros per kilogram of pollutant, representing the loss of economic welfare that occurs when an extra kilogram of a pollutant is released into the environment. The methodology includes midpoint characterization factors compatible with the ReCiPe 2016 framework, ensuring compatibility with the LCA-eCBA symbiosis. The **Handbook** provides prices at the European level (EU27) for the year 2021. This report will use the central case values recommended by the Handbook.

Using these environmental prices, we can assess the monetary value of the environmental impacts quantified by the LCA as part of the InBestSoil project. The values of these impact categories would be multiplied by the respective prices to estimate the external costs associated with these environmental impacts (Figure 3).

Data adjustments and aggregation

When applying the benefit transfer methodology, the original data should not be used directly. Instead, **adjustments are required to harmonise the information between studies**, ensuring well-defined value estimates for the target application areas. These adjustments must be consistent with the value definition, the valuation context, the theoretical basis of the value transfer, and the information available at the study site and policy site (Johnston et al. 2021).

For this case study, unit value transfer adjusted for spatial differences (EU prices) was applied. Damage cost estimates provided by the Handbook (EU27 average) were adapted to Spain, Croatia, Lithuania, Latvia, Italy, Netherlands, and Switzerland, assuming similar utility functions. As WTP for environmental quality increases with income, values were adjusted to reflect differences in income levels.

A major challenge in international benefit transfer is the variation in income levels and prices across countries. On the one hand, the national environmental prices should be correlated to the national income level (GDP per capita). On the other hand, there are important differences between countries in the value of an amount of money (e.g., 100 €), in terms of the quantity of goods and services it can buy (because of differences in prices). In that case, monetary comparisons must be done according to the purchasing power parity (PPP) of currencies. Within the European Union, GDP per capita in PPP terms (GDPpc PPP) differs between countries (Ready & Navrud, 2006). To account for these differences, GDPpc PPP was used as a proxy for income to translate the environmental prices provided by the Handbook (EU27 average) to the national context, following international recommendations for benefit transfer (Biausque, 2012).

The **spatial adjustment** was performed using an income elasticity of WTP (β) of 0.65, in line with the latest update of the Environmental Prices Handbook (2024). For EU countries, GDPpc PPP data for 2021 were obtained from [Eurostat](#) and expressed in euros. For Switzerland, which is not part of the euro zone, GDPpc PPP values were derived through a specific calculation procedure. PPP data originally expressed in Swiss francs were first converted into euros using the corresponding CHF–EUR conversion factor, ensuring consistency with the EU27 dataset.

Spatially adjusted WTP values were calculated applying the formula:

$$WTP_C = WTP_{EU27} (Y_C / Y_{EU27})^\beta$$

Where Y represents GDP per capita in PPP terms, $EU27$ refers to the reference study and C to the country of application, and β is the income elasticity. This procedure ensures a harmonised spatial adjustment across both euro and non-euro countries, allowing the inclusion of Switzerland without introducing distortions related to currency or purchasing power differences.

The InBestSoil project includes a heterogeneous collection of LH and LL, which makes cross-country comparisons useless. That means there is no benefit of using monetary valuations in PPP terms. Accordingly, national environmental prices were converted to Local Current Prices to make them comparable with data provided by the technoeconomic analysis from deliverable D3.2 - *Economic valuation of ecosystem services and disservices in LHs* (WP3, InBestSoil) (financial costs and benefits).

Additionally, a **temporal adjustment** is required since the environmental prices refer to the year 2021 (De Bruyn et al. 2023), and technoeconomic values and ecosystem services refer to 2024. Besides, we should account for the increase in income levels over time, due to the positive income elasticity of willingness to pay (WTP). Therefore, similarly to the territorial adjustment, an income-based adjustment is applied to update values over time. We estimated the WTP in 2024 based on the 2021 reference as follows:

$$WTP_{2024} = WTP_{2021} (Y_{2024} / Y_{2021})^\beta$$

Where Y_{2024} and Y_{2021} are GDP per capita in current prices at different points in time (source [Eurostat](#)), and β is the income elasticity of the demand for the environmental good. This temporal adjustment reflects changes in income levels over time as a result of changes in real income and prices.

As shown in Table 1, the adjusted environmental prices reflect the socio-economic diversity of the study sites. For instance, the valuation of Global Warming impacts ranges from 0.09 €/kg CO₂-eq in Croatia and Latvia to 0.32€/kg CO₂-eq in Switzerland. These differences are strictly correlated with the differences in purchasing power and economic growth (GDP current prices) between 2021 and 2024, ensuring that environmental externalities are economically assessed according to the local economic context of each InBestSoil case study

Finally, it should be noted that the **environmental costs** calculated through the LCA-e-CBA framework **cover the entire value chain (cradle-to-gate approach)**. Consequently, a substantial share of the impacts may occur outside the physical boundaries of the managed or restored areas. This includes upstream impacts, such as those from the production of external inputs (e.g. fertilizers or chemical products). Including these stages allows for a more complete estimation of the net environmental costs of the management practices implemented.

Table 1. Summary of the environmental prices (€ per unit of impact) for the EU27 (2021) and selected European countries (2024), derived using spatial and temporal adjustments

Impact categories	Units	Central value UE-27 (*)	Spain	Croatia	Italy	Latvia	Lithuania	Netherlands	Switzerland
Global warming (GWP)	€/kg CO ₂ eq	0.13	0.12	0.09	0.14	0.09	0.10	0.21	0.32
Stratospheric ozone depletion (ODP)	€/kg CFC-11-eq	29.1	27.9	19.1	31.1	19.7	22.5	46.2	72.5
Ionizing radiation (IR)	€/kBq Co-60-eq	0.00422	0.00405	0.00277	0.00452	0.00286	0.00326	0.00669	0.01052
Ozone formation, Human health (OF-HH)	€/kg NO _x -eq	1.86	1.79	1.22	1.99	1.26	1.44	2.95	4.63
Fine particulate matter formation (PMF)	€/kg PM _{2.5} -eq	84.7	81.3	55.7	90.6	57.3	65.5	134.4	211.0
Ozone formation, Terrestrial ecosystems (OF-TE)	€/kg NO _x -eq	0.416	0.399	0.273	0.445	0.281	0.322	0.660	1.037
Terrestrial acidification (TA)	€/kg SO ₂ -eq	5.28	5.07	3.47	5.65	3.57	4.08	8.38	13.16
Freshwater eutrophication (FE)	€/kg P-eq	3.74	3.59	2.46	4.00	2.53	2.89	5.93	9.32
Marine eutrophication (ME)	€/kg N-eq	14.25	13.68	9.37	15.25	9.64	11.02	22.61	35.51
Terrestrial ecotoxicity (TET)	€/kg 1,4-DCB-eq	0.00064	0.00061	0.00042	0.00068	0.00043	0.00049	0.00102	0.00159
Freshwater ecotoxicity (FET)	€/kg 1,4-DCB-eq	0.0209	0.0201	0.0137	0.0224	0.0141	0.0162	0.0332	0.0521
Marine ecotoxicity (MET)	€/kg 1,4-DCB-eq	0.0032	0.0031	0.0021	0.0034	0.0022	0.0025	0.0051	0.0080
Human carcinogenic toxicity (HCT)	€/kg 1,4-DCB-eq	3.99	3.83	2.62	4.27	2.70	3.08	6.33	9.94
Human non-carcinogenic toxicity (HNCT)	€/kg 1,4-DCB-eq	0.071	0.068	0.047	0.076	0.048	0.055	0.113	0.177

(*) Values taken from the Handbook of Environmental Prices 2024 - ReCiPe 2016 midpoints, in €2021 per unit for EU27

3.3. INTEGRATION OF MANAGEMENT COSTS AND PRODUCTION BENEFITS IN THE E-CBA FRAMEWORK

After quantifying environmental costs through monetisation of environmental impacts, financial data were integrated to complete the e-CBA framework (see Figure 4). For each Living Lab (LL) and Lighthouse (LH), investment costs, operation and maintenance (O&M) costs, and production revenues were combined with environmental externalities to estimate the overall socioeconomic balance.

The economic dataset from the deliverable D3.2 provides a harmonised market-based valuation of soil uses across agricultural, forestry, and urban systems. This information is based on technical data provided by LL/LH experts and case study leaders (e.g., inputs, labour, yields, and management characteristics), complemented by statistical sources when needed. This ensures methodological consistency across case studies.

In addition to market values (costs and revenues), D3.2 also provides non-market monetary estimates of ecosystem services. In this framework, social value is captured through the monetisation of environmental externalities (environmental costs and ecosystem services). D3.2 provides monetary estimates of ecosystem services according to spatial adjustment (GDP per capita in PPP terms). As explained previously, the full integration of all costs and benefits required the conversion of those values in PPP to Local Current Prices, to make them comparable with data provided by the technoeconomic analysis (financial costs and benefits). To ensure consistency, all values are expressed in €/ha per year. That means investment cost should be annualised (e.g., implementation of Technosols in LH2 and LH3, or tree planting in LH6). A lifetime of 68 years was assumed for Technosols and 20 years for forest systems, in line with D3.2.

Figure 4. Integrated e-CBA framework for Social Margin Calculations

This harmonised treatment allows direct comparison between O&M costs, annualised investments, production revenues, and environmental externalities, enabling the estimation of net social balances for each soil management system (Figure 4).

4. Results

This section presents the consolidated e-CBA results derived from the analysis of 9 case studies, including 7 Lighthouses (LH) and 2 Living Labs (LL), covering a diverse range of European soil uses. These case studies cover agriculture, forestry, urban, and industrial land uses across four biogeographical regions in Europe: Boreal, Continental, Atlantic, and Mediterranean (Figure 5).

To ensure methodological consistency with the LCA, direct field emission data (measured on-site for gases like CO₂, CH₄, and N₂O) were excluded from the total environmental cost calculations. This decision was based on the fact that these specific field measurements are highly sensitive to short-term climatic and seasonal conditions, which could introduce significant uncertainty and bias into long-term assessments.

Consequently, the **analysis focuses strictly on management-related impacts**, such as machinery operations, transport, and the production of inputs, ensuring a reliable, transparent, and robust evaluation of the environmental costs directly associated with soil management practices.

Figure 5. Overview of the nine case studies within the InBestSoil project (LH 1-7 and LL 8-9)

4.1. INDUSTRIAL SOILS

LH2 – MEDITERRANEAN INDUSTRIAL SOIL (CARTAGENA, SPAIN): RESTORATION OF CONTAMINATED SOIL BY MINING ACTIVITIES USING ARTIFICIAL SOILS (TECHNOSOLS)

This LH is focused on the restoration of contaminated soil, severely degraded by intense mining activities which resulted in heavy metal contamination, acidification, sulfation and salinization, leading to an almost complete loss of vegetation cover (Figure 6).

Figure 6. LH2 area: before (left) and after (right) restoration

The intervention applied combines the application of artificial soils (Technosols) composed of organic (slurry and manure) and inorganic materials (mine tailings and marble waste), together with an assisted phytostabilization phase through the establishment of metal-tolerant plant species. This integrated approach was designed to immobilize contaminants, improve soil health and restore key regulating ecosystem functions.

The **total environmental cost** of the intervention was estimated as **178 €/ha**. The application of Technosols was identified as the main contributor phase, accounting 69 €/ha (39% of the total e-cost), primarily due to fuel consumption for machinery operation and material transport (Figure 7). The crop establishment phase accounted for 52 €/ha, largely driven by seedling production, which represented almost the entire environmental burden of this activity.

Figure 7. Environmental costs (€/ha) of the remediation process implemented in the LH2

Figure 8. Main impact categories contributing to the environmental costs of the intervention in the LH2

The environmental costs were concentrated in three impact categories: fine particulate matter formation (PMF: 43.4%), global warming potential (GWP: 22.9%) and human toxicity (HCT+HNCT: 26%), reflecting the **relevance of emissions related to material handling, soil amendments and establishment** activities in a heavily degraded mining context (Figure 8).

The results should be interpreted considering that no active management takes place under the non-intervention scenario. Therefore, this analysis captures the added environmental pressures generated by the restoration activities themselves.

From **a financial perspective**, adding environmental costs to the high initial investment (101,746 €/ha) results in a **clearly negative short-term balance**, as no direct market revenues are generated. However, the intervention in LH2 should be considered a one-time capital investment needed to remediate a severely degraded site. Both **investment and environmental costs occur at the beginning of the project** and no recurrent maintenance costs are assumed during the expected lifetime of the Technosols.

Therefore, the calculated environmental costs (178 €/ha) must be annualised over a 68-year period in the same way as the first investment (in line with D3.2 calculations). This resulted in an equivalent **environmental cost of 2.62 €/ha per year**, enabling a direct comparison with the annual flows of ecosystem services and ensuring methodological consistency within the e-CBA framework (Table 2). Overall, the annual environmental burden resulting is insignificant in relation to the magnitude of the restoration effort, being **only 0.17% of the total costs**.

However, the financial result does not represent the overall social value of the intervention. According to the non-market values, presented in deliverable D3.2, **the restoration generates substantial non-market benefits through improved ecosystem services**, such as soil stabilization, reduced contaminant mobility and enhanced regulating functions. The increase in ecosystem service value has been estimated at approximately 24,243 €/ha per year compared to the non-intervention baseline. Over the long term, these benefits largely offset the initial restoration investment, **resulting in a strongly positive social outcome** (+22,744 €/ha year) (Table 1).

Table 2. e-CBA performance of LH2 Forest (€/ha per year)

LH2		BS (No action)	MP (Restoration)	Δ €/ha per year
Market	Revenues	0.00	0.00	0.00
	I+O&M costs	0.00	1,496.27	1,496.27
Non-market	Environmental costs	0.00	2.62	2.62
	Ecosystem services	35,869.73	60,112.74	24,243.02
Social Margin		35,869.73	58,613.85	22,744.13

(*) Results expressed in €/ha per year. Social margin = market margin + non-market margin

LH3 – ATLANTIC INDUSTRIAL SOIL (TOURO, SPAIN) – RESTORATION OF CONTAMINATED SOIL BY COPPER MINING ACTIVITIES USING TECHNOSOLS

This case study focuses on soil restoration in an area highly affected by copper mining. The study area presented extreme degradation, including severe soil and water pollution, hyperacidification, hyperoxidation, hypersulfation, hyperaluminization and important levels of metallic contamination, among others. The remediation strategy applied consist of producing and applying artificial soils (Technosols) specifically designed to neutralize acidity, immobilize heavy metals, and improve soil structure and fertility (Figure 9).

Figure 9. LH3 area of restoration, before and after the soil intervention

In LH3, Technosols were produced using industrial and organic by-products, including ashes from combustion of woody debris biomass, (produced by the pulp mill from the ENCE factory), sewage sludge, residual aluminium gels (from aluminium extrusion industries), mussel shell waste, crushed biomass and filler from crushing amphibolite and schist to obtain road aggregates (see Figure 10).

Figure 10. Closeup of the Technosols applied in the LH3 intervention

The total environmental cost of the intervention reached **5,110 €/ha**. These impacts are entirely linked to the remediation process including Technosols production, transport, and field application.

From a process perspective, **Technosols production accounts for approximately 60%** of total environmental costs (3,100 €/ha), confirming that upstream activities related to material preparation and mixing are the main environmental hotspots. During the application phase, truck loading is the most impactful activity (898 €/ha), followed by transport to the site (667 €/ha) and soil spreading (445 €/ha) (Figure 11). These findings highlight the importance of logistics management in large-scale soil remediation projects.

Figure 11. Environmental costs (€/ha) of the remediation process implemented in the LH3

Figure 12. Main impact categories contributing to the environmental costs of the intervention in the LH3

The environmental impact is concentrated in three impact categories: **human non-carcinogenic toxicity** (HNCT, 39.6%), **fine particulate matter formation** (PMF, 30.4%) and **global warming potential** (GWP, 21.5%), reflecting the relevance of emissions linked to material handling, machinery use and transport of large volumes of Technosols constituents (Figure 12).

These results must be interpreted considering the extremely degraded baseline conditions. Under the no-action scenario, no active management takes place. Therefore, the assessment reflects only the added environmental pressures generated by the restoration works.

When the environmental costs are internalised into the **economic assessment**, the restoration have shown a **clearly negative balance**, linked to high investment costs (129,790 €/ha) and no market direct revenues generated. This measure should be understood as a one-time capital intervention aimed at restoring a severely degraded mining site. Both the **investment and the associated environmental impacts occur at the beginning of the project** and no recurrent maintenance costs are expected over the lifetime of Technosols.

So, the total environmental impacts quantified at 5,110 €/ha must be annualised over the same 68-year time horizon applied to the investment costs (consistent with the approach

in D3.2). This results in an **annual environmental cost of 75.16 €/ha per year**. Applying this temporal harmonization allows environmental costs, annualised investment costs and ecosystem service to be assessed on a comparable basis, thereby ensuring internal consistency within the e-CBA framework (Table 3).

Table 3. e-CBA performance of LH3

LH3		BS (No action)	MP (Restoration)	Δ €/ha per year
Market	Revenue	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Cost	0.00	1,908.68	1,908.68
Non-market	Environmental costs	0.00	75.16	75.16
	Ecosystem services	192,656.75	226,882.57	34,225.82
Social Margin		192,656.75	224,898.73	32,241.98

(*) Results expressed in €/ha per year. Social margin = market margin + non-market margin

Overall, the annual environmental burden resulting from this is low in relation to the size of the restoration effort, being **only 4% of the total costs**.

However, this financial result does not represent the overall social value of the intervention. According to the non-market valuation presented in deliverable D3.2, this restoration provides key benefits such as contaminant immobilisation, acid neutralisation, recovery of soil functions, reduced risks to water bodies, carbon sequestration and landscape restoration. The increase in ecosystem service value has been estimated at approximately 34,226 €/ha per year compared to the non-intervention baseline. Over the long term, these benefits largely offset the annualised costs, **resulting in a strongly positive social outcome** (+32,242 €/ha year) (Table 3).

Overall, these results illustrate that even capital-intensive remediation projects remain socially justified once environmental externalities and ecosystem service gains are jointly considered.

4.2. URBAN SOILS

LH4 –CONTINENTAL URBAN SOIL (ZAGREB, CROATIA) – CARBON SEQUESTRATION AND FLOOD MITIGATION CAPACITY OF AGRICULTURAL AND FOREST USES IN URBAN SOILS

The LH4 focuses on urban soils in the continental region of Zagreb (Croatia), which are affected by long-term overexploitation and unsustainable land management. The reference soil is characterised by low organic carbon content, soil compaction, structural degradation, reduced biodiversity, land abandonment and an increased risk of flooding. These conditions limit the capacity of urban soil to provide key ecosystem services, particularly water regulation and carbon sequestration. For that, the restoration efforts focus on the **application of different sustainable management practices including**

mulching, minimal soil disturbance, permanent grass cover and optimised fertilization, which significantly improve soil health.

The study compares two different areas where sustainable soil management practices have been implemented (grassland and apple orchard), together with a nearby control area under annual cropland management (see Figure 13).

Figure 13. Overview of LH4 land uses (from left to right): annual cropland, apple orchard, and grassland

Figure 14. Environmental costs (€/ha) of the management practices implemented in the LH4

Environmental costs vary substantially across land uses, reflecting differences in management intensity and input requirements (Figure 14). The lowest environmental costs are associated with grasslands, with a total of 31 €/ha. This system is characterised by low-intensity practices, mainly mulching activities and permanent vegetation cover, with no soil disturbance and no fertilization.

In contrast, the **apple orchard presents the highest reaching 438 €/ha. Fertilization is the dominant contributor** to environmental burden, accounting for more than 50% of total environmental costs (230 €/ha). Despite the adoption of sustainable practices such as mulching and permanent grass cover, the higher input intensity needed to sustain fruit production leads to increased emissions, particularly related to climate change, human toxicity and ecotoxicity-related impact categories. This result highlights that input-intensive operations remain a key environmental hotspot, even under improved management strategies.

The conventional **annual cropland has shown relatively high environmental costs (344 €/ha)**, driven mainly by **soil preparation and harvesting activities**. These two stages together account for more than 65% of total environmental costs, reflecting high diesel consumption and intensive machinery use. This combined with intensive mineral fertilisation, further contributes to the environmental burden of this system.

Overall, grassland management reduces environmental costs by 91% compared to conventional annual cropland, while the apple orchard increases environmental costs by approximately 27% compared to the baseline. These results clearly demonstrate the strong influence of land use and management intensity on environmental performance.

Differences across systems are also observed in the variations through impact categories contributions (Figure 15). **Grassland management shows a strong reduction in human toxicity** (cancer effects) linked to the absence of fertilizers and pesticides. In addition, **marine eutrophication (ME) plays a significant role in conventional cropland** but is negligible in the sustainable alternatives, with reductions of 78% for the apple orchard and 98% for grasslands. This pattern is directly linked to the reduced nutrient losses associated with permanent vegetation cover and improved soil structure.

These results confirm that sustainable soil management practices in urban areas can substantially reduce environmentally relevant pressures, particularly those related to nutrient losses and toxic emissions.

Figure 15. Seven main impact categories contributing to the environmental costs of the intervention in the LH4

The integration of environmental externalities (environmental costs and ecosystem services) into economic assessment is illustrated in Table 4 and Figure 16

The **annual cropland (baseline)** system, characterised by conventional tillage, intensive mineral fertilisation and the absence of cover crops or mulching, shows high environmental costs (344 €/ha) and production costs (1,353 €/ha), while revenues from winter wheat production are relatively low (857 €/ha). This results in an almost neutral or slightly negative economic balance even before environmental externalities are considered. When environmental costs are included, the system becomes **clearly inefficient from both an environmental and economic perspective (-840 €/ha)**. Environmental costs represent 20% of total costs, underlining the importance of including externalities in economic evaluations.

The **apple orchard** under sustainable management presents the highest environmental costs (438 €/ha), but it also generates substantially higher economic benefits (11,130 €/ha), despite relatively high production costs (6,416 €/ha). As a result, the integrated analysis indicates a strongly positive economic balance (+4,276 €/ha), suggesting that the economic value of apple production is sufficient to compensate for the associated environmental costs. In this system, environmental costs represented only the 9% of total costs, suggesting that high-value production can absorb environmental externalities when sustainable practices are applied.

For **grasslands**, the absence of direct market costs prevents calculations.

Table 4. e-CBA performance of LH4 Forest (€/ha per year)

LH4		Annual cropland (BS)	Apple orchard	Δ €/ha per year
Market	Revenues	857.00	11,130.00	10,273.00
	Management costs	1,353.00	6,416.00	-5,063.00
Non-market	Environmental costs	343.93	437.89	-93.96
	Ecosystem services	15,292.74	14,322.14	-970.59
Social Margin		14,452.81	18,598.25	4,145.45

Overall, both systems are socio-economically efficient once ecosystem services are accounted for (Figure 16). However, the apple orchard achieves a higher net social gain due to the combination of substantial market revenues and sustained provision of ecosystem services (Table 4), demonstrating that soil-health-oriented management can align private profitability with broader societal benefits.

Figure 16. Integrated socio-economic balance (€/ha per year) of the annual cropland and the sustainably managed apple orchard (LH4)

LH5 – BOREAL URBAN SOIL (VILNIUS, LITHUANIA) – IMPACT OF URBAN AGRICULTURE ON SOIL HEALTH

This LH focuses on soil threats of boreal urban soils like flood risk, soil erosion, compaction, pollution, reduced biodiversity and low organic content. The intervention consists in the implementation of **sustainable urban gardening**, including a variety of crops (cucumber, tomato, onion, pumpkin and strawberries), and practices such as composting, mulching, no tillage and the avoidance of agrochemicals (Figure 17).

Figure 17. Photos of the LH5 intervention: aerial view of the site and detailed view of the urban garden analysed

The **environmental costs** associated with urban gardening practices implemented in LH5 amount to a total of **6 €/ha** (Figure 18). Analysing the contribution per activity, **land management practices** (including composting or mulching) are **the main driver of environmental costs**, accounting for 72% of the total, together with fertilisation contributing 22% while irrigation has a negligible contribution, reflecting the low intensity or limited use of water inputs in the system.

Figure 18. Environmental costs (€/ha) of the urban gardening practices implemented in LH5

In terms of **impact categories**, Human toxicity (carcinogenic and non-carcinogenic) is the dominant category, accounting for 47% of total costs. This is followed by global warming potential (GWP) and fine particulate matter formation (PMF), each contributing 23%, while all remaining categories individually contribute 3% or less, showing a limited relevance in the overall impact profile (Figure 19).

Figure 19. Main impact categories contributing to the total environmental costs in LH5

When environmental costs are incorporated into the economic assessment, the LH5 intervention shows a clear **contrast between environmental burden and management effort** (Table 5). While environmental costs are minimal (6 €/ha), production costs are relatively high (198 €/ha), reflecting the labour-intensive nature of urban gardening and soil improvement practices such as composting, mulching and diversified cropping.

Market revenues from vegetable production (e.g. cucumber, tomato, onion) amount to 335 €/ha, resulting in a modest but positive private margin. If only direct costs and revenues are considered, the practice can be characterised by **low environmental impact and limited but positive economic performance**.

However, the overall contribution of LH5 extends beyond direct revenues. Total ecosystem services valuation was estimated at 32,144 €/ha per year, highlighting substantial social and environmental benefits. This value reflects the comprehensive social valuation of the urban garden, and therefore it is specific to the land-use option assessed. Nevertheless, this assessment does not include the performance under alternative urban green space designs or management schemes. For instance, a full CBA should consider alternative uses like a grass garden (i.e., it will provide an extra 4,900 €/ha of ES, will provide zero revenues, and different management and environmental cost). Unfortunately, the data provided by this case study is limited and prevents us from doing all these calculations.

Table 5. e-CBA performance of LH5 (€/ha/year)

LH5 – Urban Garden		€/ha per year
Market	Revenues	335
	Management costs	198
Non-market	Environmental costs	6
	Ecosystem services	32,144.33
Social Margin		32,274.68

Consequently, when **externalities are integrated** into the e-CBA framework, the social margin reaches 32,275 €/ha per year, clearly showing a **strongly positive social value**. Environmental costs are only around 3% of total private costs, reinforcing that LH5 constitutes a low-impact urban land-use option with moderate economic performance but substantial socio-environmental value, contributing primarily to local food provision and community benefits.

4.3. AGRICULTURAL SOILS

LH7 – ATLANTIC AGRICULTURAL SOIL (BETUWE, NETHERLAND) – REGENERATIVE CROP MANAGEMENT FOR IMPROVED NUTRIENT CYCLES AND SOIL HEALTH

The LH7 focuses on an agricultural soil where sustainable methods are applied to improve soil health. These biodynamic and regenerative practices, consist of broad crop rotations, use of green manure, reduced tillage, and the use of nitrogen-fixing crops (Figure 20). This intervention was compared against a conventional system with the aim of evaluating and quantifying the impact that these practices have on soil health enhancement.

Management in the **biodynamic and regenerative system** relies on organic seeds, green manures, reduced tillage and no use of chemical inputs. In contrast, the **conventional system** uses conventional seeds, mineral fertilizers, herbicides and fungicides and reliance on external inputs for pest control and soil fertility.

Figure 20. Photos of the biodynamic and regenerative systems under study

The monetisation of environmental impacts reveals **substantial differences between conventional and organic** crop management systems. Total environmental costs **decreased by 33% when shifting from conventional to organic management**, falling from 696 €/ha to 467 €/ha (Figure 21), highlighting the overall environmental advantage of biodynamic and regenerative practices.

The results also confirmed a clear shift in the sources of environmental pressure. In the **conventional system, agricultural machinery is the main contributor** to environmental costs (524€/ha), followed by fertilisation and pest management. In contrast, under organic management machinery-related costs decrease by 43% and fertilization costs by 77%. Environmental costs linked to synthetic pesticides are fully eliminated.

Conversely, sowing with organic seeds shows a higher environmental cost compared to conventional seeds, reflecting more resource-intensive seed production processes, but this increase is widely compensated by reductions in all other management stages.

Figure 21. Environmental costs (€/ha) of the two farming systems under study in LH7

Figure 22. Main impact categories contributing to the environmental costs of the two farming systems in LH7

About impact categories, organic management reduces costs in almost all categories. The most significant reduction is observed for **global warming potential (-57%)**, ionising radiation (-88%), human carcinogenic toxicity (-79%), freshwater eutrophication (-78%), and terrestrial ecotoxicity (-78%) (Figure 22). These reductions are mainly linked to the absence of synthetic fertilisers and pesticides and to the lower fuel consumption. Only marine eutrophication increases, rising from 10 to 20 €/ha, though its contribution to total costs is still limited.

When environmental costs are internalised in the economic analysis, the results clearly favour the organic system. As shown in the Table 6, while **conventional farming supports a small positive private margin (107 €/ha)**, when environmental costs are included, the system becomes negative (-588.72 €/ha), showing that the environmental damage exceeds the economic profit.

In contrast, the **organic system generates a positive balance**, supported by lower management costs (1,681 €/ha), higher revenues (3,210 €/ha), and reduced environmental costs. This shows that regenerative and biodynamic practices not only reduce environmental externalities but also improve overall socio-economic efficiency (Figure 23).

In both systems studied, **environmental costs are a substantial share of production costs: about 20%**. This shows that these impacts are a significant part of the full cost of farming. Ignoring these often-overlooked costs can give a wrong picture of economic performance of agricultural systems and lead to poor management decisions. Including them in the e-CBA framework is essential for clear, complete, and useful sustainability assessments.

Figure 23. Revenues, management costs (investment + O&M) and environmental costs for conventional and organic farming in LH7

By incorporating the valuation of ecosystem services (ES), a broader sustainability perspective is provided, internalising both negative externalities (environmental costs) and positive externalities (ecosystem services) (Table 6). Organic management increases the value of economic services by 19% compared to conventional farming. Consequently, the **social margin under organic management reaches 24% higher than the conventional**

system (an absolute increase of +7,457 €/ha per year). These results prove that organic management is not only a viable economic alternative but also a necessary strategy for supporting social and environmental sustainability in Atlantic agricultural systems.

Table 6. e-CBA performance of LH7 (€/ha peryear)

LH7		Conventional (BS)	Organic	Δ €/ha per year
Market	Revenues	2,413.00	3,210.00	797.00
	Costs	2,306.00	1,681.00	-625.00
Non-market	Environmental costs	695.72	467.10	-228.62
	Ecosystem services	31,155.38	36,961.53	5,806.15
Social Margin		30,566.66	38,023.43	7,456.77

The results of LH7 show that **organic and regenerative management reduces environmental pressures, improves economic performance, and increases social value**, reinforcing its relevance as a sustainable pathway for improving soil health and nutrient cycling in Atlantic agricultural systems.

LL1 – MEDITERRANEAN AGRICULTURAL SOIL (SARDINIA, ITALY) – ALTERNATIVE CROP MANAGEMENT AS POTENTIAL CLIMATE CHANGE MITIGATION AND ADAPTATION

The intensive agricultural practices and increase challenge environmental conditions driven by climate change are deteriorating soil fertility and health in the Mediterranean region. This degradation diminishing agricultural profitability and leading to the abandonment of cultivated land.

Intervention in LL1 was focus on the application of conservation agriculture incorporating a set of practices focused on conserving water and soil through reduced soil disturbance (reduced tillage and sod seeding), permanent soil cover, and crop rotations (see Figure 24).

Figure 24. Photographs from LL1 show the conventional tillage and sod seeding management practices

Environmental costs associated to the practices implemented in LL1 highlights the considerable influence of soil management on overall environmental performance (Figure 25). Under **conventional tillage, total environmental costs amount to 281 €/ha**. Sowing represents the largest contribution (approximately 50% of total costs), mainly due to impacts associated with seed production and machinery use, including fuel consumption. Soil preparation and crop maintenance also account for significant shares of the overall environmental burden (76 and 63 €/ha, respectively), while harvesting has a marginal contribution (4 €/ha).

About the two sustainable practices analysed, **reduced tillage** significantly lowers environmental costs, with a **24% reduction compared to conventional tillage** (total e-costs 213 €/ha). This improvement is mainly explained by the substantial decrease in impacts associated with soil preparation (8 €/ha). On the other hand, **sod seeding achieves the lowest environmental burden**, with total costs of 205 €/ha (**27% reduction** compared to the conventional baseline). In this system, soil preparation is eliminated, which explains the added reduction observed relative to reduced tillage (Figure 25).

Figure 25. Environmental costs (€/ha) of the remediation process implemented in the LL1

Figure 26. Main impact categories contributing to the environmental costs of the intervention in the LL1

Environmental impacts are mainly driven by two categories across the three management systems: **global warming potential (GWP)** and **particulate matter formation (PMF)**.

Together, they account for **around 65–70% of total environmental costs** in all scenarios (Figure 26). In conventional tillage, GWP represents 97 €/ha and PMF 96 €/ha. A similar pattern is observed in reduced tillage and sod seeding, although absolute values decrease due to lower overall fuel consumption and reduced soil disturbance. Differences between management practices are mainly explained by variations in toxicity-related and air-emission categories. Thus, **conventional tillage shows higher contributions from human non-carcinogenic toxicity (HNCT, 10%) and ozone formation** for human health (OF-HH, 2%), which are linked to more intensive machinery use and associated fuel combustion.

An integrated economic balance for LL1 could not be performed due to inconsistencies between the LCA inventory and the economic datasets provided in D3.2.

LL2 – CONTINENTAL AGRICULTURAL SOIL (BASELLAND, SWITZERLAND) – CLIMATE MITIGATION THROUGH SOIL ORGANIC MATTER ACCUMULATION AND BUILT-UP

This Living Lab focuses on agricultural soils facing multiple sustainability challenges, including soil organic matter (SOM) depletion, loss of soil biodiversity, erosion risk, and diffuse pollution of soil and water driven by intensive farming practices. These pressures reduce long-term soil fertility and resilience, limiting the capacity of agricultural systems to contribute to climate mitigation and sustainable food production.

Two experimental sites were analysed: a **biodynamic farming system**, characterised by diversified crop rotations and reduced chemical inputs, and a **conventional farming system**, based on intensive arable production (Figure 27). Several plots within each system represent different management goals, ranging from food and feed production to ecosystem service-oriented practices, such as nectar production for pollinators and SOM accumulation without harvesting (Table 7).

Figure 27. Overview of the two different experimental sites in LL2, showing the biodynamic system (left) and the conventional system (right)

Table 7. Description of the different management strategies implemented in LL2

Agricultural system	Plots	Crops	Management practices
Biodynamic	LL2_1-3	Faba bean+triticale	crop production with mulching, shallow tillage, organic fertilization harvest
	LL2_4-6	Lentils + oats	crop production with mulching, shallow tillage organic fertilization mechanical weed control harvest
	LL2_7-9	Flowers	not harvested support pollinators by producing nectar
	LL2_13-15	Barley	not harvested accumulate SOM to enhance long term soil health and fertility
Conventional	LL2_16-18	Barley	arable plot
	LL2_19-21	Fodder (hay and silage)	intensive production
	LL2_22-24	Wheat	arable plots

Environmental costs in the **biodynamic system** show high variability across management practices, ranging from approximately **652 to 1,578 €/ha** (Figure 28).

Higher environmental costs within the biodynamic system are associated with **faba bean** (1578 €/ha) and **mountain lentils** crops (965 €/ha). In both cases, fertilisation is the dominant contributor, accounting for around 55–60% of total environmental burden. This result highlights the **environmental relevance of organic and processed fertilisers**, particularly in relation to human toxicity impact categories (carcinogenic and non-carcinogenic) (Figure 29). Soil preparation and sowing together represent approximately 20–30% of total costs, reflecting machinery use and fuel consumption. Harvesting contributes relatively little to total environmental costs (around 13% for faba bean plots and 5% for lentil plots), indicating that upstream input production and soil management are more relevant environmental hotspots (Figure 28).

Nectar production practice, designed to support pollinators and biodiversity without harvesting, present unexpectedly high environmental costs (1,270 €/ha) despite of the simplicity of this management approach. These costs are mainly driven by tillage (731 €/ha) and sowing activities (539 €/ha). The results suggest that the environmental burden is linked to intensive machinery use which is reflected in high contributions from global warming potential (GWP) and fine particulate matter formation (PMF) (Figure 29).

SOM accumulation practice shows the lowest environmental costs within the biodynamic farming system (652 €/ha). In this case, sowing operations dominate the impacts, accounting for nearly 80% of total costs, likely due to the use of complex seed mixtures application and repeated operations.

Figure 28. Environmental costs (€/ha) of the biodynamic systems analysed in the LL2

Figure 29. Contribution of the main impact categories to the total environmental costs in the different management practices under biodynamic farming systems

Environmental costs in the **conventional system** range from **116 to 1,440 €/ha**, showing strong contrasts between different crop types and management intensities (Figure 30).

Fodder production shows the lowest environmental costs (116 €/ha) among conventional practices. This low impact is explained by the absence of soil tillage, mineral fertilisation, and pesticide use, with environmental burdens mainly linked to slurry application and mowing.

Conventional **barley** production shows moderate environmental costs (310 €/ha), with soil preparation, sowing, and fertilisation contributing in relatively similar proportions. This reflects a lower-intervention annual cropping system compared to wheat.

In contrast, **wheat** cultivation presents the highest environmental costs (1,440 €/ha) among conventional practices. Nearly 50% of total costs are associated with soil preparation, driven by intensive tillage operations such as mulching and deep ploughing. This is clearly reflected in higher contributions from GWP and PMF, linked to diesel

consumption and machinery use (Figure 31). Fertilisation further increases environmental burdens, particularly in eutrophication-related categories.

Figure 30. Environmental costs (€/ha) of the conventional systems analysed in the LL2

Figure 31. Contribution of the main impact categories to the total environmental costs in the different management practices under conventional farming systems

When **external costs are incorporated into the economic assessment**, the results prove significant variability across different management practices. In most cases, internalising environmental costs significantly worsens the economic balance with only 2 scenarios maintaining a positive balance, confirming that private profitability alone does not reflect real sustainability performance (Table 8).

Table 8. Cost-Benefit Analysis (e-CBA) results for the evaluated scenarios

LL2	Biodynamic				Conventional		
	Faba bean	Lentils	Nectar production	SOM	Barley	Fodder	Wheat
Management costs	7,258	8,118	400	9,141	966	301	2,233
Revenues	4,869	9,823	0	0	277	544	471
Environmental costs	1,578	1,045	1,270	652	310	117	1,440
Social margin (*) without ES	-3,967	660	-1,670	-9,793	-999	126	-3,202
% e-costs	18%	11%	76%	7%	24%	28%	39%

All values in €/ha per year

(*) **Social margin** values include only environmental costs (negative externalities). Non-market ecosystem services (ES; positive externalities) are not accounted for due to data limitations.

Figure 32. Annual economic and environmental performance (€/ha per year) of biodynamic and conventional agricultural practices in LL2

The **lentils system** under biodynamic management **shows the strongest overall performance**. This is the only biodynamic productive crop with a positive margin after internalising environmental costs (660 €/ha), combining high private profitability with the lowest relative environmental pressure (11% of total costs).

Conversely, **conventional wheat performs worst among productive systems**, with a negative private margin (-1,762 €/ha), which increases to -3,202 €/ha when environmental costs are included. These costs are 39% of total costs, highlighting the important environmental burden of conventional wheat crops relative to the economic value generated.

It is interesting to highlight the **SOM accumulation scenario as a soil restoration strategy rather than a productive system**. Although income is zero and the private margin is negative (-9,141 €/ha), environmental costs being only 7% of total costs. This shows

minimal environmental pressure compared to financial effort, suggesting that SOM-focused practices could be environmentally efficient despite requiring short-term economic investment.

Nectar production stands out for its **high environmental impact** with environmental costs accounting for 76% of the total. This suggests that the intervention has a significant operational footprint due to the substantial use of machinery and other resources, which could be optimised. It should be noted that the current assessment does not include positive externalities, such as improved biodiversity and associated ecosystem services (e.g., pollination and pest control, delivering nectar for bees). Including these benefits could substantially alter the results, potentially lower the environmental burden, and highlight the broader ecological value of this practice.

Fodder is the only conventional crop that supports a positive margin once environmental costs are internalising (126 €/ha). The environmental costs represent 28% of total costs, and its relative environmental load is still higher than that of conventional barley or SOM accumulation, showing that economic viability is achieved at a relatively high environmental cost.

Overall, the LL2 management practices show that some biodynamic practices clearly outperform conventional system (e.g. lentils), while others involve strongly negative balances (e.g. SOM accumulation) (Figure 32). These results suggest that sustainability is driven more by crop design and specific management practices than by the production system alone.

It is important to note that the estimated social margins for LL2 are likely conservative, as specific non-market values of ecosystem service are not available for each of these scenarios. Therefore, the current assessment only captures the internalisation of negative externalities (environmental costs). As a result, the total social value is only partially reflected, excluding relevant benefits in the case of biodynamic practices such as carbon sequestration, cultural heritage functions, or biodiversity support.

4.4. FORESTRY SOILS

LH1 – MEDITERRANEAN FORESTRY SOIL (EXTREMADURA, SPAIN) – RESTORATION OF SOIL BY ROTATIONAL GRAZING MANAGING IN WOODY PASTURES

Mediterranean forestry soil is characterised by low biodiversity, erosion risk, overgrazing, reduced soil organic matter and overall low soil quality. To address these soil threats, a sustainable management strategy based on regenerative rotational grazing has been implemented (Figure 33). This practice avoids tillage and sowing, applies short periods of high grazing intensity followed by sufficient resting time and uses autochthonous cattle and sheep breeds.

The goal of this practice is to improve soil structure, enhance vegetation cover, increase soil organic matter, and promote biodiversity, while maintaining productive land use through meat production.

Figure 33. Photos of the Mediterranean forestry soil abandoned (left) and under rotational grazing practices (right)

Environmental costs associated to the management practice implemented in LH1 amount to **354 €/ha**, reflecting that the environmental burden is mainly driven by livestock-related activities (livestock emissions: 89 €/ha, and feeding: 238 €/ha) accounting for more than 99% of the total environmental costs (Figure 34). This highlighted that the animal production processes in the central role in the overall environmental performance of this practice applied in the Mediterranean soil.

Among impact categories, **global warming is the dominant contributor, representing 33% of total environmental costs (104 €/ha)**, followed by human non-carcinogenic toxicity (112 €/ha) and fine particulate matter formation (67 €/ha). These three categories together account for over 80% of total environmental costs, indicating that climate-related emissions, toxicity linked to feed production and handling, and air pollution are the main environmental pressure points of the system. Other relevant contributions arise from terrestrial acidification (7.3%) and marine eutrophication (5.4%), both closely linked to nutrient losses and feed-related emissions (Figure 35).

Figure 34. Environmental costs (€/ha) of the restoration practice implemented in the LH1

Figure 35. Main impact categories contributing to the environmental costs of the intervention in the LH1 (accounting more than 99% of the total environmental costs)

Overall, the results indicate that the environmental performance of LH1 is largely determined by **animal-related processes**, especially feed production and associated emissions, suggesting that mitigation strategies targeting feed composition, sourcing, and livestock management could yield substantial reductions in total environmental costs.

When environmental costs are integrated in the economic assessment, the rotational grazing system implemented in LH1 shows a **negative economic balance**. Despite relatively low management costs (253 €/ha) and moderate revenues from livestock production (175 €/ha), the inclusion of environmental costs (354 €/ha) substantially affects the overall performance, resulting in a net balance of -432 €/ha. **Environmental costs account for 58% of total costs**, highlighting their significant weight in the economic assessment and the relevance of internalising environmental externalities when evaluating land management practices.

Table 9. e-CBA performance of LH1 Forest

LH1		Forest
Market	Revenues	175
	Costs	253
Non-market	Environmental costs	354.15
	Net ES benefits	17,389.88
Social Margin		17,137.73

(*) Results expressed in €/ha per year. **Social margin** = market margin + non-market margin

However, this result should be interpreted alongside the ecosystem services (ES) valuation reported in D3.2, which shows that the transition to rotational grazing leads to an overall improvement in the provision of regulating and cultural services compared to the initial forest management without livestock. Although these benefits are largely non-market and therefore not reflected in production revenues, they generate a positive net social value of +17,390 €/ha per year.

Taken together, these findings underline that, while rotational grazing may appear economically inefficient when assessed solely by-market outputs, **accounting** for both negative **externalities (environmental costs)** and positive externalities (**ecosystem service benefits**) is essential to capture its true societal performance and avoid misleading conclusions based only on private profitability.

These results highlight the role of regenerative grazing as a management option to restore soil functions while supporting economic activity in Mediterranean forestry systems.

LH6 – BOREAL FORESTRY SOIL (LATVIA) – EFFECT OF FERTILIZATION, SELECTION OF SPECIES, TREE BREEDING AND SUSTAINABLE SOIL MANAGEMENT

The main soil threats in this area include low below- and aboveground biodiversity, erosion, GHG emissions, low soil quality with risk of nutrient deficiency, low soil organic matter content, landscape simplification, soil acidity, and inappropriate groundwater levels.

Since 2001, the area representative of high soil health has been designated as a research territory, where sustainable management practices have been implemented to keep high soil health (Figure 36). These practices include nutrient balance management, reforestation to promote vegetation cover, tending to improve light conditions for specific species, and gentle soil preparation techniques

Figure 36. Photos of some different practices applied in the forestry soils of LH6

The results confirm that sustainable management practices applied in boreal forestry soils are associated with low **total environmental costs, amounting to around 80 €/ha**. (Figure 37).

These environmental costs are **mainly driven by recultivation activities**, which represent 46% of total, mainly related to machinery use, especially during soil preparation phase. Soil conditioning is the second most important contributor, accounting for 23% (19 €/ha). This impact is mainly linked to the use of soil pH correction materials, such as calcium carbonate, whose extraction and processing are energy intensive. **Planting activities also contributed noticeably** (15% of the total costs, 12 €/ha), reflecting the environmental burden associated with tree seeding production.

Figure 37. Environmental costs (€/ha) of the restoration practice implemented in the LH6

From an impact category perspective, environmental burden was dominated by GWP (34%) and FPM (32%), followed by human toxicity related impacts (together representing about 25% of total environmental costs) (Figure 38). These results are coherent with the LCA findings, which highlighted machinery use, soil conditioning materials and limited use of plant protection products as the main environmental hotspots.

Figure 38. Main impact categories contributing to the environmental costs of the intervention in the LH6

Table 10. e-CBA performance of LH6 Forest (€/ha/year)

LH6		Forest
Market	Revenues	0.00
	Costs	274.26
Non-market	Environmental costs	15.61
	Net ES benefits	490.86
Social Margin		200.99

(*) Results expressed in €/ha per year. **Social margin** = market margin + non-market margin

When environmental costs are integrated into the economic assessment, the **LH6 intervention shows a negative market balance** due to investment and management costs (274 €/ha per year) and the absence of current revenues from wood production (Table 10). It is expected that future timber sales could provide additional income, potentially improving private margins over time.

The monetised environmental costs were originally calculated at 80 €/ha, but a large part of these are associated with re-cultivation, planting and soil conditioning activities, which should be considered as long-term investments rather than annual operating costs. When annualised over a 20-year period (consistent with D3.2) a direct comparison with recurrent market costs and private margins is allowed, reinforcing the consistency of the e-CBA. Thus, the **annual equivalent environmental cost of 16 €/ha per year** indicates a **moderate environmental burden relative to economic effort**, being 5.5% of the total costs.

Despite the negative economic balance, the intervention generates substantial ecosystem service benefits, such as supporting services contributing most and a net increase in non-market value of **475 €/ha** compared to the abandoned area (based on the non-market valuation reported in D3.2). Overall, the **social margin of the restoration is positive (+201 €/ha per year)**, proving that, although economically unattractive from a market perspective, the intervention delivers a clear positive societal value.

5. Conclusions

The integration of Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and environmental Cost-Benefit Analysis (e-CBA) within the InBestSoil project provides a robust framework to evaluate soil management. By translating environmental impacts associated with the restoration and alternative practices into a common monetary metric (€), this approach reveals "hidden" costs often ignored in traditional economic assessments.

The results of this analysis lead to several key conclusions:

- The study reveals that **environmental costs are a significant part of the real cost of land management, accounting for 20% to 60% of total costs** in several cases. Assessments based solely on private profitability may therefore be misleading. In some cases (e.g., conventional agricultural systems), practices that appear financially viable generate net social losses once environmental externalities are internalised. This directly supports the Soil Mission objective of making the value of soil health measurable and visible.
- Evidence from **agricultural** systems (e.g., LH7) shows that **switching to organic and regenerative practices can reduce environmental costs by 33%** while simultaneously improving socio-economic value. However, the analysis also identifies "hotspots," such as the intensive use of machinery in several biodynamic systems (e.g., LL2), suggesting that even sustainable practices must be optimised to reduce their operational footprint.
- In **urban** contexts (LH4, LH5), **sustainable practices** like grasslands or urban gardening show a strongly **positive net social benefit** due to their low environmental impact and high provision of ecosystem services, demonstrating the economic rationale for soil-based urban interventions.
- For severely degraded **industrial** and mining sites (LH2, LH3), the high initial financial and environmental costs of restoration using Technosols are justified as one-time capital investments. These costs are largely offset by the long-term recovery of vital ecosystem services, resulting in **strongly positive social outcomes**.
- In Mediterranean **forestry** (e.g., LH1), regenerative grazing shows that while these practices might have higher environmental costs due to livestock, they generate significant social value through improved soil health and biodiversity. This highlights that a **positive social margin often justifies practices that may seem less efficient from a purely market-based perspective**.
- The LCA–eCBA framework serves as a practical tool for identifying environmental "hotspots" and designing management systems that are both economically viable and ecologically resilient. These results provide a scientific basis for policymakers at the national and EU levels to design incentives, such as subsidies or regulations, that support the objectives of the EU Soil Mission.

In summary, the InBestSoil e-CBA framework establishes a methodological foundation for upscaling sustainability assessments. The results demonstrate that sustainable soil management is not only an environmental necessity but also a socio-economic strategy.

Using Euros (€) as a single metric allows policymakers to compare biophysical impacts with economic reality, making the value of natural capital visible.

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